

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY

Prateek Gupta,
SRM University, India

REVIEWED BY

Feng Zhang,
CABI, China
Luis F. Aristizabal,
Consultant, Kailua-Kona, United States

*CORRESPONDENCE

Luca Cappellin
✉ luca.cappellin@unipd.it

RECEIVED 31 January 2024

ACCEPTED 29 October 2024

PUBLISHED 28 November 2024

CITATION

Favaro R, Berka M, Petterson M, Thöming G, Arce CCM, Inácio ML, Turlings TCJ, Faria JMS, Jung T, Bazin D, Pozzebon A, Angeli S and Cappellin L (2024) The use of volatile organic compounds in preventing and managing invasive plant pests and pathogens. *Front. Hortic.* 3:1379997. doi: 10.3389/fhort.2024.1379997

COPYRIGHT

© 2024 Favaro, Berka, Petterson, Thöming, Arce, Inácio, Turlings, Faria, Jung, Bazin, Pozzebon, Angeli and Cappellin. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The use, distribution or reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice. No use, distribution or reproduction is permitted which does not comply with these terms.

The use of volatile organic compounds in preventing and managing invasive plant pests and pathogens

Riccardo Favaro¹, Miroslav Berka², Martin Petterson³, Gunda Thöming³, Carla C. M. Arce⁴, Maria L. Inácio⁵, Ted C. J. Turlings⁴, Jorge M. S. Faria^{5,6}, Thomas Jung⁷, Damien Bazin⁸, Alberto Pozzebon⁹, Sergio Angeli¹⁰ and Luca Cappellin^{1*}

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Padova, Padova, Italy, ²Department of Molecular Biology and Radiobiology, Faculty of AgriSciences, Mendel University in Brno, Brno, Czechia, ³Division of Biotechnology and Plant Health, Norwegian Institute of Biotechnology Research, As, Norway, ⁴Faculty of Science, Institute for Biology, University of Neuchâtel, Neuchâtel, Switzerland, ⁵INIAV, I.P., National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinary Research, Oeiras, Portugal, ⁶GREEN-IT Bioresources for Sustainability, Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Oeiras, Portugal, ⁷Department of Forest Protection and Wildlife Management, Mendel University in Brno, Brno, Czechia, ⁸R&D Department, Chromatotec, Saint-André de Cubzac, France, ⁹Department of Agronomy, Food, Natural Resources, Animals, Environment (DAFNAE), University of Padova, Padova, Italy, ¹⁰Faculty of Agricultural, Environmental and Food Sciences, Free University of Bolzano, Bolzano, Italy

Invasive pests and plant pathogens pose a significant threat to ecosystems and economies worldwide, prompting the need of anticipatory strategies. Preventing their introduction by detection at the ports of entry has been proven extremely difficult. This review explores the potential of biogenic volatile detection as a reliable preventive solution. It underscores the importance of early detection and rapid response as integral components of effective invasive pest management, and it discusses the limitations of current control measures and the increasing globalization that facilitates the spread of pests and pathogens. Through a synthesis of existing literature, this review analyzes the Volatile Organic Compound (VOC) emissions in five invasive model species: three insects, *Halyomorpha halys*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, a nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, and an oomycete, *Phytophthora ramorum*. The review focuses on the specific volatiles, released by both the invasive organisms and the infested host plants. If available, the volatiles emitted from similar species were considered for comparison. Ultimately, this review highlights specific pest volatile and shared Herbivore Induced Plant Volatiles (HIPVs) as a reliable and innovative solution in pest detection. If possible, candidate compounds are provided, whilst the lack of some emphasizes the urge of expanding the information available.

KEYWORDS

headspace, VOC collection, detection, *Halyomorpha halys*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, *Phytophthora ramorum*

1 Introduction

In the global context of agriculture, the continuous threat posed by quarantine and severe pest species has become a pressing concern for researchers, policymakers, and farmers. The expansion of international trade and travel has facilitated the inadvertent spread of invasive pests, resulting in substantial economic losses and ecological imbalances worldwide. Management of these pests can be achieved through several approaches, but the most used ones are harmful chemicals, such as insecticides and fungicides in plant protection. The reduction by 50% of pesticide use is among the proposals adopted by the European Commission, in line with the EU's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies (EC, 2020b). To achieve this goal, it is important to control new pest invasions and already established pests. The detection of invasive pests is a fundamental aspect of contemporary agricultural practices and ecological conservation. Swift and accurate detection allows for the implementation of timely control measures, preventing the establishment and spread of invasive species, minimizing economic and ecological impacts (MacDougall et al., 2022). One innovative approach to enhance the detection of invasive pests involves exploiting the volatile organic compounds (VOCs) released by the target pests or induced in attacked plants (Cui et al., 2018). Insects and pathogens produce VOCs as a mean of communication (semiochemicals in insects) or as metabolic derivatives (Bos et al., 2013; Gullan and Cranston, 2014; Fennine et al., 2024). Plants use VOCs to interact with other plants and insects, by luring pollinators, recruiting an herbivore's adversaries, camouflaging other plants, spotting invading plants, alerting other plants to impending danger, and exhibiting allelopathy (Baldwin, 2010; Heil, 2014; Karban et al., 2014; Turlings and Erb, 2018; MacDougall et al., 2022; Schuman, 2023). Once attacked by an enemy (either animals, fungi, bacteria, virus or nematodes), plants change their volatile profile induced volatiles (Dicke et al., 2009). They are a plant defense mechanism released by plants attacked by herbivores as a signal for higher trophic levels or other plants (Paré and Tumlinson, 1999; Gebreziher, 2018; Turlings and Erb, 2018; War et al., 2011).

The unique chemical signatures of these VOCs serve as indirect early warning signals, enabling to identify the presence of invasive pests before establishment and significant damage occur (Cui et al., 2018). These volatile signals can be used as valuable cues for monitoring and identifying pest infestations, enabling timely interventions, reducing potential crop damage and optimizing pest management strategies (MacDougall et al., 2022). Nixon et al. (2018), proposed to use the compounds released by *Halyomorpha halys* to detect the diapausing insects in shipments and selected possible target VOCs after a Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. Similarly, pest VOCs were taken into consideration to detect the presence of bed bugs (Akhoundi et al., 2023), a serious human health-related issue. Forty-nine compounds emitted by *Cimex lectularius* L. and *C. hemipterus* Fabricius through their life stages were considered as valuable indicators of the bug presence. The same approach has also been proposed for the detection of a pine fungal pathogen,

Fusarium circinatum Nirenberg & O'Donnell (Nordström et al., 2022), where through VOCs collection, GC-MS and automated data analysis, they managed to correctly distinguish infested and healthy seedlings of *Pinus radiata* Don and *P. sylvestris* L.

Volatiles can be collected in various ways (Brezolin et al., 2018; Tholl et al., 2021). Pre-concentration of VOCs on solid adsorbents followed by thermal desorption has become one of the standard methods for both field and laboratory studies. The type of adsorbent must be carefully selected to match the physicochemical characteristics of the target compounds. Additionally, the time from sampling to analysis must be minimized to prevent sample degradation due to reactive gases like ozone. However, most commercially available adsorbents work well, and they can be stored for a long time in a freezer without severely affect the outcomes of the analysis (Chu et al., 2016; Ho et al., 2018, authors personal observation). Among the different analytical techniques available for VOC analysis, including Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometry (PTR-MS) or electronic e-nose, Gas chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) has proven to efficiently separate and identify trace levels of VOCs in complex mixtures. However, both PTR-MS and GC-MS requires the use of large, expensive laboratory equipment that is unsuitable for use in the field. Moreover, the collection, processing, and analysis of the samples is time consuming and requires trained people. Therefore, for timely detection of pest, rapid and accurate diagnostic techniques that can be applied in the field are required. Efforts to achieve this goal have focused on the employment of so-called electronic noses to identify plant diseases and pests. An electronic nose uses a variety of gas sensors in conjunction with techniques for feature extraction and pattern recognition to identify and differentiate between distinct odors. The work of Fundurulic et al. (2023) provides an overview of the most recent developments in the field and emphasizes the application of cutting-edge methods for the prompt, non-destructive identification and control of harmful plant pests. Still, deploying e-nose for accurate and reliable characterization of specific VOCs in the field requires addressing challenges like sensor stability, specificity and reproducibility.

This review provides a context on the biology and, importantly, summarizes the current knowledge on the signature VOCs of five invasive pest model species: the brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha halys*), the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*), the pinewood nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) and *Phytophthora ramorum*. They are three insects, a nematode and an oomycete, and they were chosen because of their relevance to the EU pest surveillance programs. Induced volatiles released by attacked plants are also reported. The purpose of this review goes beyond the evaluation of the scientific soundness of the reference works, as they span a time of decades and a wide array of VOC collection techniques. It aims instead at presenting the current state of available information on VOCs of some relevant key pests, defining, when possible, a list of candidate VOCs for the pest identification to be used in pest surveillance and monitoring. The candidate VOCs were selected following the criteria of specificity and consistency. Specificity refers to the quality of clearly define or identify the target pest, whilst reducing unrelated false positive

signals. Consistency on the other hand is crucial for scientific reproducibility and defines uniformity and stability of measurements over time and across different conditions or experiment. Therefore, findings that were confirmed by multiple studies were accounted as reliable. Each pest is presented in a dedicated section, reporting the biology, the management and its related VOCs.

2 Volatile organic compounds produced and induced by *Halyomorpha halys*

2.1 The brown marmorated stink bug: distribution, biology and management

Halyomorpha halys (Stål) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), known as the Brown Marmorated Stink Bug (BMSB) (Figures 1A, B), is an insect native to eastern Asia, and is now considered one of the most harmful invasive pests in North America and Europe (Zobel et al., 2016).

Halyomorpha halys consumes plant juices for nutrition feeding on the green parts of the plant, such as leaves and stems, but fruits are typically preferred (Figure 1C). The most significant crop damage comes from piercing fruiting structure on pome, stone and other fruit crops as well as seeds in legume pods such as soybeans (Leskey and Nielsen, 2018). The fruits are Highly deformed in cases of severe infestations, and there may be significant financial losses (Zobel et al., 2016). Fruit attacked by *H. halys* showed also increase in damage by fruit pathogens (Rice et al., 2014; Moore et al., 2019). The economic implications in the agricultural production are considerable, reaching billions of euros in crops worldwide (Rice et al., 2014). From a detailed estimation conducted in Northern Italy, it has emerged that it causes damages in the production of pears, apples, peaches, and kiwis for an estimated economic loss of 740 million euros (Fornasiero et al., 2023). In the eastern USA, the effects on apple and peach orchards reached up to total loss in 2010 (Leskey et al., 2012).

Due to its extreme polyphagia, *H. halys* has roughly 40 hosts among domesticated plants and much more (around 300) wild hosts (EPPO Global Database, 2023). *Halyomorpha halys* has one or two generations per year in the USA and Europe, but there have been reports up to 5–6 generations per year in the species' native range (Lee et al., 2013; Haye et al., 2014; Costi et al., 2017). In its adult stage, the stink bug spends the winter in natural shelters or anthropogenic structures. On the underside of the leaves, in clusters of 20–30 eggs, females lay 50–150 eggs, but they can also lay up to 400 eggs per female. There are five nymphal stages before reaching the adult stage (Lee et al., 2013) (Figure 1B). The control of *H. halys* relies on insecticides (Leskey et al., 2012). Recently, adventive populations of Asian egg parasitoid *Trissolcus* spp. (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae), in particular *Trissolcus japonicus* Ashmead and *Trissolcus mitsukurii* Ashmead were discovered in America and Europe (Talamas et al., 2019; Abram et al., 2019; Stahl et al., 2019; Sabbatini Peverieri et al., 2018; Scaccini et al., 2020) and may serve as viable antagonists. Other

management options for the control of *H. halys* are staking, trap crops, perimeter reshaping in orchards, push-pull, exclusion nets, and behavioral manipulation. These had the potential to drastically minimize fruit loss (e.g., Blaauw et al., 2015; Candian et al., 2020; Falagiarda et al., 2023; Fornasiero et al., 2023; Camio et al., 2024).

The use of semiochemicals plays an important role in the management of this pest. The discovery of the pest aggregation pheromone (Khrimian et al., 2014) opened for further pest control strategies. It is solely produced by adult males, and it attracts both adult males, adult females, and nymphs (Weber, 2015). For this reason, the pheromone lures are employed in traps for monitoring, early detection (Vandervoet et al., 2019) and for pest management decision making.

2.2 Summary of literature on *Halyomorpha halys* VOCs

Numerous studies have identified and characterized the volatile compounds emitted by *H. halys* (Table 1). These volatiles primarily consist of a diverse array of aldehydes, alcohols, esters, terpenes, and sulphur-containing compounds. Some of the most notable compounds include the aldehydes (*E*)-2-decenal, (*E*)-2-octenal, (*E*)-2-hexenal, sesquiterpenes and alkanes. The composition and ratios of these volatiles can vary depending on factors such as developmental stage, sex, feeding status, and environmental conditions.

Stink bugs, including *H. halys*, possess specialized scent glands located on their thorax and abdomen that release volatiles when disturbed or threatened (Kitamura et al., 1984). The emission of volatiles is primarily a passive process, relying on the release of pressure built up within the scent gland reservoir. These defense compounds are shared among many species and (*E*)-2-decenal, (*E*)-2-octenal, (*E*)-2-hexenal, (*E*)-2-decenyl acetate are reported in not only *H. halys* (Harris and Webber, 2016; Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018, 2019, 2021; Karimi and Gross, 2024), but also in a cosmopolitan species, the green stink bug *Nezara viridula* L. (Aldrich et al., 1987). These volatiles were collected from either full insect after immersion in solvent (Zhong et al., 2017) or from headspace by using different adsorption materials: Super-Q (Khrimian et al., 2014; Harris and Webber, 2016; Nixon et al., 2018, 2019, 2021), Tenax (Karimi and Gross, 2024), activated charcoal (Aldrich et al., 1987).

Generally, these (*E*)-2-aldehydes are reported as defensive compounds inducing avoidance by predators (Noge et al., 2012), and likely connected to the disturbance level the insects are exposed (Nixon et al., 2021). It was showed that they function also as alarm pheromones (Harris and Webber, 2016), acting as warning signal to conspecifics, indicating the presence of threats, and as dispersal signals, causing other stink bugs to disperse quickly, reducing the likelihood of multiple individuals being preyed upon simultaneously (Nixon et al., 2018, 2021). The implication of these VOCs in an intraspecific context is supported by the data reported in Nixon et al. (2021), in which the proportion of samples that released these defensive odors was null in singularly agitated insects, whilst increased proportionally to the number of insects in the group. Khrimian et al. (2014) characterized the male-produced

FIGURE 1

Pests and representative disease symptoms. **(A–C)** Brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha halys*). Scale bar = 1 cm. **(A)** Adult bug (photo courtesy: Diana La Forgia, Agroscope, Switzerland). **(B)** Eggs (left) and newly hatched nymphs (right) (photo courtesy: Carole Paroli, Agroscope, Switzerland). **(C)** Apple with sucking damage (arrows) (photo courtesy: Veronica Carnio, Free University of Bolzano, Italy). **(D, E)** Fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*). **(D)** Mature caterpillar with distinctive inverted Y suture on the forehead (photo courtesy: Neil Villard, University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland). Scale bar = 1 cm. **(E)** Fall armyworm frass and feeding damage in a maize field in Rwanda (photo courtesy: Stefan Toepfer, CABI, Switzerland). **(F–H)** Cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*). Scale bar = 1 cm. **(F)** Mature caterpillar on *Chrysanthemum* flower (photo courtesy: Erling Floistad, NIBIO, Norway). **(G)** Mature caterpillar with frass and feeding damage on a sunflower leaf (photo: Gunda Thöming). **(H)** Damage caused by caterpillar frass on tomato fruits (arrows) (photo: Gunda Thöming). **(I)** Male Pinewood Nematode (PWN; *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) with characteristic pointed tale. Scale bar = 100 nm (photo courtesy: INIAV, Portugal). **(J)** *Monochamus galloprovincialis*, main vector of the PWN in Europe. Scale bar = 1 cm (photo courtesy: INIAV, Portugal). **(K)** Mature *Pinus pinaster* tree in Portugal showing acute wilting and mortality caused by the PWN (photo courtesy: INIAV, Portugal). **(L)** Natural *Pinus densiflora* forest on Amami Island, Japan with high mortality due to PWN damage (photo: Thomas Jung).

TABLE 1 List of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) released by *Halyomorpha halys* and *Nezara viridula* (A), and list of Herbivore Induced Plant Volatiles (HIPVs) released by *H. halys*-infested plants (B) described in the literature.

A. Insect volatiles				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>H. halys</i> , adult male	(3S,6S,7R,10S)-10,11-Epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol	–	1	Khirmian et al., 2014; Harris and Webber, 2016; Weber, 2015
<i>H. halys</i> , adult male	(3R,6S,7R,10S)-10,11-Epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol	–	1	Khirmian et al., 2014; Harris and Webber, 2016; Weber, 2015
<i>H. halys</i> , adult, nymph, male genital capsule; <i>N. viridula</i> , adult	Tridecane	629-50-5	1	Aldrich et al., 1987; Tognon et al., 2017; Harris and Webber, 2016; Fraga et al., 2017; Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018;
<i>H. halys</i> , adult, eggs; <i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(E)-2-Decenal	3913-81-3	1	Aldrich et al., 1987; Sturaro et al., 1994; Harris and Webber, 2016; Tognon et al., 2017; Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	(E)-2-Decen-1-ol	22104-80-9	1	Kitamura et al., 1984
<i>H. halys</i> , adult; <i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(E)-2-Decenyl acetate	19487-61-7	1	Aldrich et al., 1987; Zhong et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , adult; <i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(E)-2-Hexenal	6728-26-3	1	Aldrich et al., 1987; Solomon et al., 2013; Zhong et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	(E)-2-Octenal	2548-87-0	2	Kitamura et al., 1984
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	(E,E)-2,4-Hexadienal	142-83-6	1	Solomon et al., 2013
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	(Z)-Cyclodecene	935-31-9	1	Solomon et al., 2013
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	1-Ethyl-1,5-cyclooctadiene	5194-50-5	1	Solomon et al., 2013
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	3-Hepten-2-one	1119-44-4	1	Solomon et al., 2013
<i>H. halys</i> , adult, eggs	2,4-Decadienal	25152-84-5	1	Kitamura et al., 1984; Tognon et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	4-Oxo-(E)-2-hexenal	2492-43-5	2,1	Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	5-Ethyl-2(5H)-furanone	2407-43-4	1	Solomon et al., 2013
<i>H. halys</i> , adult; <i>N. viridula</i> , adult	Dodecane	112-40-2	1	Kitamura et al., 1984; Aldrich et al., 1987; Borges et al., 1987; Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	Pentadecane	629-62-9	1	Kitamura et al., 1984
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	Tetradecane	629-59-4	1	Kitamura et al., 1984
<i>H. halys</i> , adult	Undecane	1120-21-4	1	Kitamura et al., 1984
<i>H. halys</i> , eggs	Hexadecanal	629-80-1	1	Tognon et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , eggs	Octadecanal	638-66-4	1	Tognon et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , eggs	Eicosanal	2400-66-0	1	Tognon et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , eggs	Nonanal	124-19-6	1	Tognon et al., 2017
<i>H. halys</i> , eggs	2-Undecenal	53448-07-0	1	Tognon et al., 2017
<i>N. viridula</i> , adult	Nonadecane	629-92-5	2,1	Aldrich et al., 1987; Borges et al., 1987
<i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(Z)- α -Bisabolene	29837-07-8	1	Aldrich et al., 1987
<i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(E)-Nerolidol	40716-66-3	1	Aldrich et al., 1987
<i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(E,Z)- α -Bisabolene epoxide	20767-74-6	1	Aldrich et al., 1987
<i>N. viridula</i> , adult	(Z,Z)- α -Bisabolene epoxide	1746-04-3	1	Aldrich et al., 1987

(Continued)

TABLE 1 Continued

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Peach (<i>Prunus persica</i> L.)	4'-Ethylacetophenone	937-30-4	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Peach	(E)- β -Caryophyllene	87-44-5	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Peach	(Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate	3681-71-8	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Peach	4-Hexenyl, acetate	72237-36-6	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Peach	Benzaldehyde	100-52-7	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven (<i>Ailanthus altissima</i> (Mill.) Swingle)	2,4-Di- <i>tert</i> -butylphenol	96-76-4	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	(E)- β -Ocimene	3779-61-1	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Methyl palmitate	112-39-0	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	(E)-Nerolidol	40716-66-3	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Sesquirosefuran	39007-93-7	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	(3E)-4,8-Dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene	19945-61-0	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Alloocimene	3016-19-1	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Cinerone	-	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	(E)-Farnesene epoxide	-	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Linalool	78-70-6	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	Nonanal	124-19-6	2	Peterson et al., 2022
Tree of heaven	<i>p</i> -Mentha-1,3,8-triene	18368-95-1	2	Peterson et al., 2022

The ID level reports the VOCs identification levels reported by the literature (1= identified compound, 2= putatively identified compound, based upon physicochemical properties of a chemical class and/or by spectral similarities). The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

aggregation pheromone of *H. halys* as a 3.5:1 mixture of two stereoisomers, (3S,6S,7R,10S)-10,11-epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol and (3S,6S,7R,10S)-10,11-epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol. According to Harris and Webber (2016), mature males started producing pheromone at a mean age of 13 days. Males who were housed alone produced a mean of 843 ng of pheromone per day, in daily volatile collections in levels that ranged fivefold. Males in groups emitted <10% pheromone per bug per day than lone males due to a strong negative reaction to male density. The pheromone is mainly emitted during the day and it is effective to both adult sexes and nymphs (Weber, 2015).

An array of linear hydrocarbons has been detected in *H. halys*: undecane, dodecane, tridecane and pentadecane (Kitamura et al., 1984; Baldwin, 2010; Harris and Webber, 2016; Zhong et al., 2017). Among them, tridecane was the most frequently found. Linear hydrocarbons are also reported among the emissions of *N. viridula*: dodecane, tridecane and nonadecane (Borges et al., 1987). It is unclear whether these volatiles might play a role as bioactive compounds (Weber, 2015). A likely explanation proposed that such hydrocarbons serve as solvents or carriers (Calam and Youdeowei, 1968), as they would facilitate the efficient evaporation of active substances such as aldehydes on the scent gland system in a variety of pentatomid species (Kment and Vilimova, 2010). However, behavioral studies showed that the

exposure of adult *H. halys* to the insect most abundant alkane, tridecane, led to an increased speed (Lockwood and Story 1985, 1987; Nixon et al., 2018), total distance and mean angular velocity (Nixon et al., 2021), and it also significantly reduced the emission of pheromones in adult males (Harris and Webber, 2016). This evidence might reveal a possible biological function of tridecane, but its mechanisms have yet to be understood. As addressed by Weber (2015), the data proposed by Harris and Webber (2016) lack statistical significance and should be considered carefully. On the other hand, the more recent work from Nixon et al. (2021) shows statistically sound evidence of an actual tridecane effect on the stink bugs behavior. It is worth considering however, that tridecane has always been found in all samples of *H. halys* VOCs studies, despite a more occasional presence of the *E*-2-aldehydes (Aldrich et al., 1987; Tognon et al., 2017; Harris and Webber, 2016; Zhong et al., 2017; Nixon et al., 2018), opening up a question on the biological relevance of an ubiquitous compound.

2.3 Summary of literature on *Halyomorpha halys* - induced plant VOCs

Despite the relevance of *H. halys* on crops worldwide, only one study has so far explored the HIPVs released after infestation. Peterson

et al. (2022), analyzed direct and systemic emissions of potted peach (*Prunus persica* L.) and tree of heaven (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle) plants following insect feeding and oviposition. The VOCs were collected from the headspace of a bag-enclosed branch for 24 hours by using a Hayesep adsorbent (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and later eluted in dichloromethane and analyzed in GC-MS. The study showed a species-specific response in the VOCs released. Nerolidol was released at a greater rate by tree of heaven branches that were directly exposed to *H. halys* oviposition and feeding than by branches exposed to only feeding and control trees. In comparison to plants exposed to oviposition and feeding or control trees, tree of heaven leaves treated to *H. halys* feeding alone emitted greater rates of (*E*)-4,8-dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene. On the other hand, when peaches were subjected to *H. halys* oviposition, there was a reduction in (*Z*)-3-hexenyl acetate in both the directly and systemically exposed branches. Other compounds in peach plants varied between treatments: 4'-ethylacetophenone, (*E*)- β -caryophyllene, 4-hexenyl acetate and benzaldehyde. Similarly in tree of heaven plants, differences appeared between treatments: 2,4-di-tert-butylphenol, (*E*)- β -ocimene, methyl palmitate, sesquirosefuran, alloocimene, cinerone, (*E*)-farnesene epoxide, linalool, nonanal, *p*-mentha-1,3,8-triene.

2.4 Candidate VOCs for *Halyomorpha halys* detection

So far, the most unique compounds are the two stereoisomers (3*S*,6*S*,7*R*,10*S*)-10,11-epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol and (3*R*,6*S*,7*R*,10*S*)-10,11-epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol, identified as the main components of the aggregation pheromone released by adult males. All the other VOCs (Table 2) are generic of stink bugs or other organisms. It is however worth considering the aldehydes (*E*)-2-decenal, (*E*)-2-octenal, (*E*)-2-hexenal and the ester (*E*)-2-decenyl acetate, the unpleasant odors released by stink bugs when disturbed (alarm/defense pheromones). These VOCs, even if very generic, can at least indicate presence of stink bugs. Tridecane, the most frequently compound detected from *H. halys* and other stink bugs, occurs commonly in the environment as it is largely emitted by biotic and abiotic sources. The candidate VOCs here selected should answer to

TABLE 2 List of candidate Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) for *Halyomorpha halys* detection.

VOC name	CAS-Nr	Biological relevance
(3 <i>S</i> ,6 <i>S</i> ,7 <i>R</i> ,10 <i>S</i>)-10,11-Epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol	-	Aggregation pheromone
(3 <i>R</i> ,6 <i>S</i> ,7 <i>R</i> ,10 <i>S</i>)-10,11-Epoxy-1-bisabolene-3-ol	-	Aggregation pheromone
(<i>E</i>)-2-Decenal	3913-81-3	Defense/alarm pheromone
(<i>E</i>)-2-Decenyl acetate	19487-61-7	Defense/alarm pheromone
(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenal	6728-26-3	Defense/alarm pheromone
(<i>E</i>)-2-Octenal	2548-87-0	Defense/alarm pheromone

The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

a specificity requirement, and therefore tridecane, due to its ubiquitous nature, has not been considered. The question on whether plants may respond in a similar way after an insect attack is crucial to increase the number of candidate HIPVs. Induced compounds that would be shared among a considerable number of host plant species following *H. halys* infestation would be extremely valuable as candidates for detection. However, the scarce literature available does not provide enough confidence to select any HIPVs, and more plant species need to be tested.

3 Volatile organic compounds produced and induced by *Spodoptera frugiperda*

3.1 The fall armyworm: distribution, biology and management

The Fall Armyworm (FAW), *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J. E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), is native to the Americas (Todd and Poole, 1980) and has been reported to attack a wide range of host plants and causes serious damage to many economical plants (Kenis et al., 2022). Although the larvae (Figure 1D) are known to feed on many host plants, they exhibit a preference for grasses and cereal crops like maize (Figure 1E), rice, sorghum, and wheat (Sparks, 1979; Pitre and Hogg, 1983). The high invasiveness potential of *S. frugiperda* is attributed to the exceptional capacity of the adult moths to migrate (Johnson, 1987; Westbrook et al., 2019). *Spodoptera frugiperda* has invaded all of sub-Saharan Africa after it was first observed in Nigeria in 2016 (Cock et al., 2017; Day et al., 2017) and also made its way from Africa to Asia (Sharanabasappa et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020). More recently it was found in Oceania (Day et al., 2017; Lamsal et al., 2020) and entered continental Europe in 2024 (<https://www.fao.org/fall-armyworm/monitoring-tools/faw-map/en/>). It is now one of the biggest threats to food security on multiple continents (FAO, 2020), causing tremendous yield losses, especially in maize (Day et al., 2017; Baudron et al., 2019; Hruska and Gould, 1997; Rwomushana et al., 2018; Wan et al., 2021), threatening the livelihoods of millions of farmers and the food security of over 65 million people in Africa alone (Day et al., 2017; Rwomushana et al., 2018; Babendreier et al., 2020) (Figure 1E). According to estimates, it causes in maize up to 73% of global economic losses (Guo et al., 2018). In Africa, *S. frugiperda* alone results in annual yield losses of 9.4 billion US dollars (Eschen et al., 2021). Between 2017 and 2019, the pest reduced Ethiopia's grain yield by 0.225 million tons, with an average yearly loss of 36% in maize production (Abro et al., 2021). According to De Groote et al. (2020), the pest results in losses of around one-third of Kenya's yearly maize crop, or one million tons, with significant regional variations.

As a consequence of the *S. frugiperda* invasion, the use of pesticides has dramatically increased (Tambo et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2021), potentially causing health problems, harming the environment, and threatening biodiversity. The FAO considers *S. frugiperda* one of the most important threats to food security in

these regions (<http://www.fao.org/fall-armyworm/en/>). Management of *S. frugiperda* involves, however, not only chemical insecticides but a wide array of integrated pest management strategies (Kenis et al., 2022). Many pathogens (bacteria, fungi, viruses), parasitoids (Diptera and Hymenoptera), and predators (Coleoptera, Dermaptera, Hemiptera, Hymenoptera) attack it throughout its natural habitat. Of all the natural enemies, egg parasitoids are the simplest to raise in high quantities for augmentative releases, and several studies are testing its viability (Vieira et al., 2017; Firake and Behere, 2020). Experiments on host plant choice have been carried out throughout the pest invasive range, mostly to look at the viability of intercropping and push-pull control techniques (Tay et al., 2023). Biopesticides involving entomopathogenic fungi, baculoviruses, entomopathogenic bacteria and nematodes have also been extensively explored (Kenis et al., 2022).

Research on the chemical ecology of *S. frugiperda* has focused on two aspects: the pheromone produced by the female moths to attract males, and the caterpillar-induced plant volatiles that attract natural enemies of the caterpillars. The sex pheromone of *S. frugiperda* is a blend of several volatile acetates, dominated by (Z)-9-tetradecenyl acetate (Z9-14:Ac). A combination of Z9-14:Ac with (Z)-7-dodecenyl acetate (Z7-12:Ac) is highly attractive to males in the field (Tumlinson et al., 1986), also to invasive populations in Japan (Wakamura et al., 2021). In a study in China a pheromone lure was optimized by still adding (Z)-11-hexadecenyl acetate (Z11-16:Ac) to the blend that was initially identified. Indeed, the *S. frugiperda* pheromone blend has been shown to be different for different geographic regions (Batista-Pereira et al., 2006; Groot et al., 2008). *Spodoptera frugiperda* was one of the first insects studied in the context of herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs). Maize plants in particular are very responsive to caterpillar attacks and have been shown to emit large amounts of mainly terpenoids, but also indole in response to such attacks (Tumlinson et al., 1990; Turlings et al., 1993). The emissions of the truly inducible compounds are systemic and not just limited to the damaged site (Turlings and Tumlinson, 1992), enhancing their detectability. The fatty acid-amino acid conjugate volicitin (N-[17-hydroxylinolenoyl]-L glutamine) present in the caterpillar oral secretions was found to be the main elicitor that triggers this response (Alborn et al., 1997; Turlings et al., 2000). *Spodoptera frugiperda* also emits such volatiles (Turlings et al., 1993), but to a lesser extent, possibly because it is able to somewhat suppress the emissions (De Lange et al., 2020). There is tremendous variation among maize genotypes in the amounts of volatiles that they release upon caterpillar attack (Degen et al., 2004), yet the overall volatile profile shows clear consistencies in their caterpillar-induced emissions (Hoballah et al., 2002; Gouinguéné and Turlings, 2002; Gouinguéné et al., 2003). Studying the *S. frugiperda*-maize model is therefore has not only a great economic importance, but also an ideal model to demonstrate the potential of odor-based detection technologies (Turlings and Erb, 2018; Turlings and Degen, 2022).

3.2 Summary of literature on *Spodoptera frugiperda* - related VOCs

The literature on volatiles directly emitted by *S. frugiperda* is limited to publications on the identification of the sex pheromone blend emitted by female moths. The first identification was done by extracting the pheromone directly from the female moth glands (Sekul and Sparks, 1967), which composition is different from the pheromone released by the moths (Tumlinson et al., 1986). The female moths were found to release (Z)-7-dodecenyl acetate (Z7-12:Ac), dodecanyl acetate (12:Ac), 11-dodecenyl acetate (11-12:Ac), (Z)-9-tetradecenyl acetate (Z9-14:Ac), and (Z)-11-hexadecenyl acetate (Z11-16:Ac). To the best of our knowledge, this latter publication is the only one that used the dynamic headspace technique to collect and identify the sex pheromone of *Spodoptera*, including *S. frugiperda*. The composition of the sexual pheromone of two closely related species, *S. exigua* and *S. frugiperda*, can be distinguished by the exclusive presence of the 12:Ac, Z7-12:Ac and 11-12:Ac in the *S. frugiperda* sex pheromone blend. Tests on the biological function of Z7-12:Ac have shown that it is the main compound responsible for the attraction of males (Tumlinson et al., 1986; Andrade et al., 2000; Cruz-Esteban et al., 2018). Their concentration is not very accurate, and composition and ratios of volatiles can vary depending on factors such as developmental stage, sex, feeding status, and environmental conditions. In subsequent studies it was shown that Z9-14:Ac and Z7-12:Ac are universal pheromone components of *S. frugiperda*, but other compounds, such as Z9-12:Ac, Z11-16:Ac and E7-12:Ac were also found to be released in different geographic populations (Tumlinson et al., 1986; Descoins et al., 1988; Fleischer et al., 2005; Batista-Pereira et al., 2006; Groot et al., 2008; Lima and McNeil, 2009; Jiang et al., 2022). In addition to the pheromone work, considerable information is available on plant volatiles induced by the caterpillars of *S. frugiperda* and other *Spodoptera* species have been extensively studied (Turlings and Erb, 2018; Turlings and Degen, 2022). In Table 3 we list the most relevant papers on inducible volatiles emitted by maize plants. It is important to note that different varieties of maize were used in different studies and they were also conducted under varying conditions ranging from the laboratory to the field. It can be concluded that different induction techniques and *Spodoptera* species induce similar volatile profiles. *S. frugiperda* does not appear to differ from other species in the volatile profile that they induce in maize plants, but there are quantitative differences, resulting in differences in ratios among VOCs that may facilitate the detection of specific pest species. For maize plants attacked by *S. frugiperda* and other *Spodoptera* species about 25 different volatiles have been reported. These include a diverse array of green leaf volatiles (GLV's), monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes and aromatic compounds. Some of the most notable compounds include (Z)-3-hexenyl acetate, linalool, indole, (3E)-4,8-dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene (DMNT), (3E, 7E)-4,8,12-trimethyl-1,3,7,11-tridecatetraene (TMTT) and (E)- β -farnesene. The release of the GLVs is induced within seconds, whereas the others are released after 4 to 6 hours after *S. frugiperda* attack (terpenoids and indole) small maize plants typically release these compounds at rates of 50-200 ng per hour.

TABLE 3 List of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) released by *Spodoptera frugiperda* and *S. exigua* adult females (A), and list of Herbivore Induced Plant Volatiles (HIPVs) released by damaged plants (B) described in the literature.

A. Insect volatiles				
Pest developmental stage	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female	Dodecanyl acetate	112-66-3	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female	7-Dodecenyl acetate	16677-06-8	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female	11-Dodecenyl acetate	35153-10-7	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female; <i>Spodoptera exigua</i> , adult female	(Z)-9-Tetradecenol	53939-27-8	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986; Tumlinson et al., 1990
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female; <i>Spodoptera exigua</i> , adult female	(Z)-9-Tetradecenol acetate	16725-53-4	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986; Tumlinson et al., 1990
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female	(Z)-11-Hexadecenal	53939-28-9	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986
<i>S. frugiperda</i> , adult female; <i>Spodoptera exigua</i> , adult female	(Z)-11-Hexadecenyl acetate	34010-21-4	1	Tumlinson et al., 1986; Tumlinson et al., 1990
<i>Spodoptera exigua</i> , adult female	(Z,E)-9,12-Tetradecadienyl acetate	31654-77-0	1	Tumlinson et al., 1990
B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Maize (<i>Zea mays</i> L.)	(Z)-3-Hexenol	928-96-1	1,2	Turlings et al., 1998b; Turlings et al., 1998a; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Indole	120-72-9	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998b; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Peñafior et al., 2011; Carroll et al., 2006; Robert et al., 2013; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	Cycloisositivene	22469-52-9	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	(3E)-4,8-Dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene	19945-61-0	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998b; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020; Yactayo-Chang et al., 2021
Maize	(3E, 7E)-4,8,12-Trimethyl-1,3,7,11-tridecatetraene	62235-06-7	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(E)-2-Hexenol	928-95-0	1	Hoballah et al., 2002
Maize	(E)-2-Hexenal	6728-26-3	1,2	Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(E)-2-Hexenyl acetate	2497-18-9	1	De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(E)-3-Hexenol	928-97-2	1,2	Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013
Maize	(E)- α -Bergamotene	13474-59-4	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al.,

(Continued)

TABLE 3 Continued

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
				2013; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; ; De Lange et al., 2020; Yactayo-Chang et al., 2021
Maize	(E)- α -Farnesene	502-61-4	1	Turlings et al., 1998a
Maize	(E)- β -Caryophyllene	87-44-5	1	Turlings et al., 1998b; Turlings et al., 1998a; Hoballah et al., 2002; Peñafior et al., 2011; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(E)- β -Farnesene	18794-84-8	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998b; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(E)- β -Ocimene	3779-61-1	1	Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Robert et al., 2013; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2016
Maize	(Z)-3-Hexenal	6789-80-6	1,2	Turlings et al., 1998a; Hoballah et al., 2002; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate	3681-71-8	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	(Z)- β -Ocimene	3338-55-4	1	De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Anthranilic acid	118-92-3	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	Benzyl acetate	140-11-4	1	Peñafior et al., 2011; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Decanal	112-31-2	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	Geranyl acetate	105-87-3	1,2	Hoballah et al., 2002; Peñafior et al., 2011; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020; Yactayo-Chang et al., 2021
Maize	Linalool	78-70-6	1,2	Turlings et al., 1993; Turlings et al., 1998a; Turlings et al., 2000; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; De Lange et al., 2016; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Methyl-anthranilate	85-91-6	1	De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Nerolidol	7212-44-4	1	Turlings et al., 1993; Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Nonanal	124-19-6	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016

(Continued)

TABLE 3 Continued

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Maize	Phenethyl acetate	103-45-7	1	Hoballah et al., 2002; Peñafior et al., 2011; De Lange et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	Ylangene	14912-44-8	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	α -Humulene	6753-98-6	1,2	Carroll et al., 2006; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	α -Muuroolene	10208-80-7	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	α -Zingiberene	495-60-3	2	Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	β -Bisabolene	495-61-4	1,2	Hoballah et al., 2002; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016
Maize	β -Sesquiphellandrene	20307-83-9	1,2	Hoballah et al., 2002; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020
Maize	β -Myrcene	123-35-3	1,2	Hoballah et al., 2002; Carroll et al., 2006; Peñafior et al., 2011; Robert et al., 2013; Pinto-Zevallos et al., 2016; De Lange et al., 2020

The ID level reports the VOCs identification levels reported by the literature (1= identified compound, 2= putatively identified compound, based upon physicochemical properties of a chemical class and/or by spectral similarities). The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

3.3 Candidate VOCs for *Spodoptera frugiperda* detection

There are three compounds that adult females of *S. frugiperda* emit (dodecanyl acetate; (*Z*)-7-dodecenyl acetate and (*Z*)-11-dodecenyl acetate) and are found only in this species compared to other species of *Spodoptera*. They have biological relevance for male attraction in the field. Plant-produced VOCs induced by *S. frugiperda* caterpillars are released in considerably larger amounts and easier to detect. As mentioned in the previous section, there are no unique compounds emitted by maize plants under *S. frugiperda* attack in comparison to attacks by other *Spodoptera* species, but ratios differences can be used to determine which species is attacking a plant. The most relevant compounds that are consistently emitted and have an ecological relevance are (*Z*)-3-hexenyl acetate, linalool, indole, (*3E*)-4,8-dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene (DMNT), (*3E,7E*)-4,8,12-trimethyl-1,3,7,11-tridecatetraene (TMTT) and (*E*)- β -farnesene (Table 4).

4 Volatile organic compounds produced and induced by *Helicoverpa armigera*

4.1 The cotton bollworm: distribution, biology and management

The Cotton Bollworm (CBW) *Helicoverpa armigera* Hübner (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Figures 1F, G) is considered as one of the major pests in tropical and warm-temperate regions worldwide (Jones et al., 2019). Global economic losses caused by this species

are estimated at over 3 billion US dollars per year (Haile et al., 2021; Riaz et al., 2021). *Helicoverpa armigera* is widely distributed throughout Asia, Oceania, Africa, and southern Europe, and has recently invaded South America (Tay et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2019).

Helicoverpa armigera is a highly polyphagous pest infesting more than 200 host plant species of diverse plant families. Many crops of high economic importance are included in its host range, such as cotton, maize, tomato (Figure 1H), sunflower (Figure 1G), soybean, and several legumes (Cunningham et al., 1999; Cunningham and Zalucki, 2014). The adults of *H. armigera* are excellent flyers and can migrate over long distances up to 2000 km (Behere et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2015). The species has a high

TABLE 4 List of candidate Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) for *Spodoptera frugiperda* detection.

VOC name	CAS-Nr	Biological relevance
Dodecanyl acetate	112-66-3	Sexual pheromone
7-Dodecenyl acetate	16677-06-8	Sexual pheromone
11-Dodecenyl acetate	35153-10-7	Sexual pheromone
(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl acetate	3681-71-8	Relevant HIPV
Indole	120-72-9	Relevant HIPV
Linalool	78-70-6	Relevant HIPV
(<i>E</i>)- β -Farnesene	18794-84-8	Relevant HIPV
(<i>3E</i>)-4,8-Dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene	19945-61-0	Relevant HIPV
(<i>3E,7E</i>)-4,8,12-Trimethyl-1,3,7,11-tridecatetraene	62235-06-7	Relevant HIPV

The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

TABLE 5 List of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) released by *Helicoverpa armigera* (A), and list of Herbivore Induced Plant Volatiles (HIPVs) released by damaged plants (B) described in the literature.

A. Insect volatiles				
Pest developmental stage	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Adult, egg, larval frass	Oleic acid	112-80-1	2,1	Guoqing et al., 2001; Liu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2006
Adult, egg, larval frass	Palmitic acid	57-10-3	2,1	Guoqing et al., 2001; Liu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2006
Adult	4-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-pentanone	123-42-2	2	Guoqing et al., 2001
Egg	Myristic acid	544-63-8	1	Liu et al., 2008
Egg, larval frass	Stearic acid	57-11-4	1	Liu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Pentadecanoic acid	1002-84-2	1	Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Methyl palmitate	112-39-0	1	Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Methyl oleate	112-62-9	1	Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Methyl linoleate	112-63-0	1	Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Methyl stearate	112-63-8	1	Xu et al., 2006
Larval frass	Linoleic acid	463-40-1	1	Xu et al., 2006
B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Cotton (<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L.)	3-Hexenyl isovalerate	10032-11-8	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	Limonene	138-86-3	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	β -Elemene	33880-83-0	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	α -Guaiene	3691-12-1	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	β -Ocimene	3779-61-1	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	δ -Cadinene	483-76-1	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	Hexenyl valerate	56922-74-8	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	TMTT	62235-06-7	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton	1-Decyne	764-93-2	1	Huang et al., 2015
Cotton, French bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>), maize (<i>Zea mays</i> L.), tobacco (<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> L.), tomato (<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> L.)	(Z)-3-Hexenol	928-96-1	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Gebrezihier and Nakamuta, 2016; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005
Cotton, maize	β -Myrcene	123-35-3	1	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006
Cotton, maize	Hexyl acetate	142-92-7	1	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006
Cotton, maize	DMNT	19945-61-0	1	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006
Cotton, maize	(E)-2-Hexenol	928-95-0	1	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005
Cotton, maize, tobacco	(E)-2-Hexenyl acetate	2497-18-9	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005
Cotton, maize, tobacco, tomato	β -Pinene	18172-67-3	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005; Gebrezihier and Nakamuta, 2016

(Continued)

TABLE 5 Continued

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Cotton, maize, tobacco, tomato	(Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate	3681-71-8	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Cotton, maize, tobacco, tomato	(E)-2-Hexenal	6728-26-3	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Cotton, maize, tomato	Linalool	126-91-0	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Cotton, tomato	α -Caryophyllene	6753-98-6	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Cotton, tomato	α -Pinene	7785-70-8	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Cotton, tomato	β -Caryophyllene	87-44-5	1,2	Huang et al., 2015; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean	Thujapsene	470-40-6	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean	1-Propanone	71-23-8	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean	Ethanal	75-07-0	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean	2-Butenol	764-01-2	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize	(E)-2-Eicosene	121909-29-3	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize	2-Butyl-1-octanol	3913-02-8	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize)	3-Methyl-2-butenol	556-82-1	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize	2-Ethyl-2-hexenal	645-62-5	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize	(Z)-2-Hexenol	928-94-9	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize, tomato	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	104-76-7	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize, tomato	D-Limonene	5989-27-5	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016; Yan and Wang, 2006
French bean, maize, tomato	o-Cymene	527-84-4	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
French bean, maize, tomato	α -Terpinene	99-86-5	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Maize	Phenylethyl acetate	103-45-7	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	Geranyl acetate	105-87-3	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	1-Octene	111-66-0	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016

(Continued)

TABLE 5 Continued

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> infestation				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Maize	Indole	120-72-9	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	(E)- α -Bergamotene	13474-59-4	2	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	(E)- β -Farnesene	18794-84-8	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	β -Sesquiphellandrene	20307-83-9	2	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	5-Methyl-2-(1-methyl ethyl)-1-hexanol	2051-33-4	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Maize	2-Ethyl-1-decanal	21078-65-9	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Maize	(E)-Nerolidol	40716-66-3	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	α -Farnesene	502-61-4	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Maize	Pentadecane	629-62-9	2	Yan and Wang, 2006
Maize	2-Ethylhexyl, 2-ethylhexanoate	7425-14-1	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Maize, tobacco	γ -Terpinene	99-85-4	1	Yan and Wang, 2006, Yan and Wang, 2006
Tobacco	Hexanol	111-27-3	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Tobacco	Methyl salicylate	119-36-8	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
	Nonanal	124-19-6	2	Yan and Wang, 2006
Tobacco	(Z)-3-Hexenyl butyrate	16491-36-4	2	Yan and Wang, 2006
Tobacco	Nicotine	54-11-5	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Tobacco	(Z)-3-Hexenal	69112-21-6	1	Yan and Wang, 2006
Tomato	3-Carene	13466-78-9	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	(E)-3-Hexenyl-acetate	3681-82-1	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	(+)-4-Carene	5208-49-1	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	β -Phellandrene	555-10-2	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	Tridecane	629-50-5	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	Tetradecane	629-59-4	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	α -Phellandrene	99-83-2	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	p-Cymene	99-87-6	2	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016
Tomato	(E)-2-Eicosene	64615-82-3	1	Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016

The ID level reports the VOCs identification levels reported by the literature (1= identified compound, 2= putatively identified compound, based upon physicochemical properties of a chemical class and/or by spectral similarities). The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

fecundity and rapid reproduction rates, resulting in average in 4-6 generations per year and up to 10-11 generations per year in tropical regions (Riaz et al., 2021). The larvae are highly destructive plant feeders and very polyphagous, not only regarding plant species but also concerning plant parts (Figures 1F–H). The species has the ability to adapt its diapause depending on environmental conditions, in order to optimize survival. All these characteristics in their biology – its polyphagy, high mobility and reproduction rates and its facultative diapause – make *H. armigera* a serious pest, quickly invading new areas.

A blind trust of synthetic pesticides as main control measure for *H. armigera* has led to resistance development to all major classes of synthetic insecticides across many regions of the world (Downes et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2019; Riaz et al., 2021). As an alternative pest control measure have genetically modified crops, such as Bt (with a toxin from *Bacillus thuringiensis*) cotton, shown a good control effect of *H. armigera* over a period. But, as for synthetic pesticides, resistant populations have developed also for Bt crops, making well deliberated resistance management strategies necessary (Jin et al., 2015; Downes et al., 2016; Tabashnik and Carrière, 2017). Today, IPM strategies based on forecast, monitoring and decision support systems combined with biological, chemical, and physical control measures must be developed and used for successful control of *H. armigera* (Downes et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2019; Riaz et al., 2021).

4.2 Summary of literature on *Helicoverpa armigera* VOCs

We focus here on studies on *H. armigera*-related VOCs, which have shown that the pest itself (4.2) or plants infested by *H. armigera* (4.3) can release herbivore-specific signals which can be measured by chemical analyzes and behavioral and/or electrophysiological bioassays. The huge number of studies regarding other issues of the chemical ecology of *H. armigera* are not included here.

Research on *H. armigera* VOCs has started in the 1970s with the identification of sex pheromones in *H. armigera*, namely (Z)-9-hexadecenal, (Z)-11-hexadecenal, hexadecanol, (Z)-11-hexadecenol

and (Z)-9-tetradecenal (Piccardi et al., 1977; Nesbitt et al., 1980; Wu et al., 1997; Zhang et al., 2012). We want to highlight here for our purpose the most promising pheromones, the oviposition marking pheromones (OMPs) or oviposition deterring pheromones (ODPs) (Table 5). ODPs have been identified for *H. armigera* around the turn of the millennium (Guoqing et al., 2001; Xu et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2008). ODPs are deposited by many parasitic and phytophagous insects associated with egg-laying, aiming for modification of the oviposition behavior of conspecifics such that subsequent eggs are not deposited into an already utilized resource. After behavioral observations on *H. armigera* have indicated the existence of oviposition-deterrent compounds, the three compounds 4-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-pentanone, hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid) and (Z)-9-octadecenoic acid (oleic acid) have been identified from the tarsi of female *H. armigera* as oviposition-deterrent compounds (Guoqing et al., 2001). In further studies on ODPs in larval frass of *H. armigera*, a blend of fatty acid and corresponding methyl esters was found in the larval frass. Some compounds were found independent of the diet of the larvae, while others seem to be dependent on the food source. All compounds elicited responses in *H. armigera* moth antennae using electroantennography (EAG) analyzes (Xu et al., 2006). Moreover, it was found that laid eggs resulted in similar EAG responses. Compounds identified from the laid eggs were the 4-oviposition deterring fatty acids myristic, palmitic, stearic, and oleic acid and their corresponding methyl esters (Liu et al., 2008).

4.3 Summary of literature on *Helicoverpa armigera* - induced plant VOCs

Another important type of *H. armigera* related VOCs is herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) (Table 5). The HIPVs emission of tobacco plants induced by larvae feeding of the sibling species *H. armigera* and *H. assulata* were studied, and the corresponding behavioral response (wind tunnel bioassay) of a main parasitoid of both species, *Campoletis chloridae* Uchida (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae), towards the different HIPV blends were recorded. GC/MS analyzes showed that β -pinene was specifically measured after feeding of *H. armigera* larvae, whereas (Z)-3-hexenal was particularly measured after infestation of both species, and hexyl acetate by mechanical damage (Yan et al., 2005). In another study, the HIPVs emission of maize plants induced by feeding of larvae of *H. armigera* and *Pseudaletia separata* Walker (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and the behavioral response of *C. chloridae* in a wind tunnel were investigated. After infestation of *H. armigera* particularly the four terpenoids β -pinene, β -myrcene, D-limonene, and (E)-nerolidol were measured. All these compounds were not measured after attack of *P. separata* or mechanical damage (Yan and Wang, 2006). Also the volatile characteristics of cotton plants after larvae infestation of *H. armigera* have been investigated. GC/MS analyzes showed that several green leaf volatiles and terpenoids were measured after *H. armigera* infestation of cotton plants, whereas other compounds

TABLE 6 List of candidate Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) for *Helicoverpa armigera* detection.

VOC name	CAS-Nr	Biological relevance
Oleic acid	112-80-1	Oviposition deterrent pheromone
Palmitic acid	57-1-01-3	Oviposition deterrent pheromone
β -Myrcene	123-35-3	Herbivore induced plant volatile
β -Pinene	18172-67-3	Herbivore induced plant volatile
D-Limonene	5989-27-5	Herbivore induced plant volatile
(E)-Nerolidol	40716-66-3	Herbivore induced plant volatile

The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

were found in both, infested and non-infested plants (Huang et al., 2015). Further studies compared by chemical analyzes the HIPV emission of tomato, French bean, and maize plants after infestation of *H. armigera* larvae, and by Y-tube olfactometer bioassays the behavioral response of the predator *Orius strigicollis* Poppius (Heteroptera: Anthocoridae). In all three plant species, a higher number and larger amounts of VOCs were found on *H. armigera* infested plants than undamaged or mechanically damaged plants (Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016). In some of these studies the odor profile of *H. armigera* infested plants have been compared with mechanical damaged plants, as both types of damage, biotic and abiotic, are stresses for the plants and induce specific VOC emission. However, to our knowledge no study compares the volatile profiles from *H. armigera*-infested plants with those of plants stressed by other abiotic factors such as water logging, drought, darkness, or extreme temperatures, or even volatile profiles of plants stressed by both, *H. armigera* infestation and abiotic factors, at the same time.

4.4 Candidate VOCs for *Helicoverpa armigera* detection

As ODPs are species-specific VOCs, detectable also in absence of the adult pest insect and identified for *H. armigera*, these compounds might be potential candidates for detection of *H. armigera*. In all three studies, we found the specific fatty acids myristic, palmitic, stearic, and oleic acid and their corresponding methyl esters have been identified as ODPs of *H. armigera* (Guoqing et al., 2001; Xu et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2008). Particularly, palmitic and oleic acid have been extracted from female moths (tarsi), larval frass and laid eggs of *H. armigera*, which might render them as robust and reliable candidates for detection purpose (Table 6).

With a view to detecting an herbivore-specific volatile blend measured from plants in response to *H. armigera* larvae feeding, we compared the volatile profiles from *H. armigera* infested plants with those from non-infested plants of different plant species found in literature. Compounds reported to be measured after *H. armigera*

larval infestation of different plant species, but not or in very small amounts only from non-infested, mechanically damaged or plants infested of another pest species, might be possible candidates for detection of *H. armigera*. The terpenoids β -pinene, β -myrcene, D-limonene, and (*E*)-nerolidol were found to be species-specific for *H. armigera* larval infestation of maize plants (Yan and Wang, 2006) (Table 6). The compound β -myrcene was found in maize and cotton particularly after *H. armigera* larval infestation (Yan and Wang, 2006; Huang et al., 2015). D-limonene was species-specific measured after *H. armigera* larval infestation on maize, French bean and tomato (Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016; Yan and Wang, 2006). A compound noticed in four different studies as species-specific volatile measured from a plant in response to *H. armigera* larvae feeding on maize, cotton, tobacco, and tomato is β -pinene (Huang et al., 2015; Yan and Wang, 2006; Yan et al., 2005; Gebreziher and Nakamuta, 2016).

5 Volatile organic compounds produced and induced by *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*

5.1 The pinewood nematode: distribution, biology and management

The Pinewood Nematode (PWN), *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* (Steiner & Buhner 1934) (Rhabditida: Aphelenchoididae), is a migratory plant parasitic nematode (Figure 11) responsible for pine wilt disease (PWD), a serious forest disease that has devastated vast pine stands in Asia and Europe (Figures 1K, L) causing substantial ecological, economic, and cultural impacts (Back et al., 2024). Originally from North America, where the incidence of *B. xylophilus* is very low due to a co-evolution between the nematode and native pine species (Sutherland, 2008), the nematode was first noted in Japan in the early 20th century Futai, 2008. *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* spread to Taiwan, China (in 1982), and Korea (in 1988), and was detected in Portugal, within the European Union, in 1999 (Mota et al., 1999). By 2008, mainland Portugal was declared a quarantine zone, and wood export

TABLE 7 List of Herbivore Induced Plant Volatiles (HIPVs) released by *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* infected plants (B) described in the literature.

B. Herbivore induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) after <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> infection				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>	Sativene	6813-05-4	2	Takeuchi et al., 2006
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>	Carvacrol methyl ether	6379-73-3	2	Takeuchi et al., 2006
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>	Camphor	76-22-2	2	Takeuchi et al., 2006
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	Limonene	138-86-3	2	Gaspar et al., 2020
<i>Pinus densiflora</i> and <i>P. koraiensis</i>	3-Carene	13466-78-9	2	Hwang et al., 2021
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>	Borneol	507-70-0	2	Wang et al., 2022

The ID level reports the Volatiles Organic Compounds (VOCs) identification levels reported by the literature (1= identified compound, 2= putatively identified compound, based upon physicochemical properties of a chemical class and/or by spectral similarities). The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

FIGURE 2

Phytophthora structures (on V8-juice agar) and typical disease symptoms (all photos: Thomas Jung). **(A)** Mature nonpapillate sporangium of the soilborne *Phytophthora x cambivora*. **(B)** Caducous sporangium of the aerial *Phytophthora ramorum* releasing zoospores (arrow). **(C)** Chlamydospore of the soilborne *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. **(D)** Oogonium of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* with mature thick-walled oospore and amphigynous antheridium. Scale bar = 20 μm and applies to **(A–D)**. **(E)** Shoot and leaf blight of a Rhododendron shrub caused by *Phytophthora ramorum*. **(F)** Stem of a mature beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) tree with an aerial bark canker with dark exudations caused by *Phytophthora plurivora*. **(G)** Stembase of a young cork oak (*Quercus suber*) tree with a bark canker with orange-brown exudations caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. **(H)** Woody roots (diameters 0.5–1.0 cm) of a mature sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) tree with bark cankers (arrows) caused by *Phytophthora x cambivora*. **(I)** Woody roots (diameters <0.6 cm) of a mature sessile oak tree with severe losses of lateral roots and fine roots caused by *Phytophthora plurivora* and *Phytophthora x cambivora*. **(J)** Acute mortality of mature cork oak trees due to girdling bark cankers at the stembase and main roots caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*.

restrictions extended nationwide (Rodrigues, 2008). *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* was found in Madeira Island in 2010 (Fonseca et al., 2012) and in Spain in 2011 (Abelleira et al., 2011), even attacking different species of *Pinus* trees (Inácio et al., 2015; Zamora et al., 2015).

The European Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) classifies *B. xylophilus* as an A2 type quarantine pest in the EU, given its extreme pathogenicity and the abundance of susceptible pines in Europe (e.g., *Pinus pinaster*, *P. sylvestris* L., and *P. nigra* Arnold) (EPPO, 2023). Although currently limited to Portugal and Spain, future climate conditions in northern Europe might create a highly susceptible environment for *B. xylophilus*, threatening northern pine forests (Hirata et al., 2017; De la Fuente et al., 2018).

The infection mechanism of PWD involves the host pine tree, an insect vector (mainly *Monochamus* sp. beetles) (Figure 1), *B. xylophilus*, and associated microbiota (Zhao et al., 2014; Vicente et al., 2012). During beetle maturation feeding, *B. xylophilus* enters healthy pines through beetle wounds, causing severe damage by invading resin canals, attacking epithelial cells, and disrupting water and mineral transport (Mamiya, 1983). This leads to pine wilting within three weeks, resulting in tree collapse within 40 to 60 days post-infection, with millions of nematodes infecting the trunk and branches (Kuroda, 2008) (Figures 1K, L). The decaying pine becomes attractive to the adult *Monochamus* beetles and, consequently, a source for new infections spread by the insect-vector (Jones et al., 2008; Futai, 2013).

Control strategies for PWD include breeding resistant pine species (Nose and Shiraishi, 2008; Carrasquinho et al., 2018; Menéndez-Gutiérrez et al., 2018) eradicating infected trees, treating wood (Kamata, 2008; Rodrigues, 2008; Xu, 2008) and controlling beetle populations. Infected wood can be treated chemically or thermally before its use for exportation or industrial purposes. Chemical insecticides prevent beetle spread, though they may harm beneficial organisms and accumulate in ecosystems (Kamata, 2008; Bi et al., 2015). Alternative controls include pheromone traps for controlling the spread of insect-vector populations and biological control using beetle predators or parasites (Nakamura, 2008; Shimazu, 2008; Kim et al., 2016). Trunk injection of nematicides is also effective, despite the toxicity risks associated with chemicals (Kamata, 2008). Integrated management strategies combining various methods are crucial for effective *B. xylophilus* containment.

5.2 Summary of literature on *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* - related VOCs

Literature on the volatiles emitted by *B. xylophilus*-infected plant material is very scarce and only six volatiles were reportedly influenced by *B. xylophilus* infection, in field and greenhouse grown infected pines (Table 7). Although no induced volatiles were reported, some constitutive pine compounds were reportedly emitted in greater proportions by the affected trees. In a study using 30-year-old *Pinus thunbergii* Parlatores trees, the proportions of sativene, carvacrol methyl ether and camphor were seen to increase, however the number of samples was low (7 infected individuals) and this

response was detected on a single tree alone (Takeuchi et al., 2006). For volatiles capture, TENAX-TA absorbent filled glass tubes were used to sample 6 L of air surrounding the stem (ca. 2h at 50 mL/min). In a different study using 2-year-old *P. thunbergii* seedlings, slightly higher proportions of borneol were signaled as a result of *B. xylophilus* inoculation in a susceptible variety (Wang et al., 2022). However, sampling was performed using SPME (65 µm PDMS/DVB) adapted to a headspace vial with 1 cm sections of 500 mg pine needles, for 30 min. For *P. densiflora* Siebold & Zuccarini and *P. koraiensis* Siebold & Zuccarini 5-year-old trees, the emission of the monoterpene hydrocarbon 3-carene was 9.7 and 54.7 times higher than in control trees, when analyzed by HS-SPME/GC-MS, by using plastic wrapped plants and analyzing with DVB/CAR/PDMS fibers (df 50/30 µm) for 1 h, at room temperature (Hwang et al., 2021). For *P. pinaster*, limonene emission was seen to increase in *B. xylophilus*-infected trees, however, this was only detected for two out of four tested trees (Gaspar et al., 2020). Sampling was performed with 1.0 g of sample/100 mL of air, using a 65 µm PDMS/DVB coated fiber with 5 min exposure time at 35°C.

5.3 Candidate VOCs for *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* detection

The available literature lacks an acceptable sample size or repeatability in results as well as variability in the conditions of sampling to conclude on suitable VOC candidates for detection of *B. xylophilus*.

6 Volatile organic compounds produced and induced by *Phytophthora*

6.1 *Phytophthora ramorum* and other important *Phytophthora* species: distribution, biology, diseases and management

The oomycete genus *Phytophthora* de Bary 1876 (Peronosporales: Peronosporaceae) currently includes eight obligate biotrophic unculturable species and ca 260 hemibiotrophic or necrotrophic culturable species and is widely distributed on all continents except Antarctica. Approximately half of the known species have been spread from their native areas to other continents where they became invasive causing severe diseases on non-coevolved host plants in horticultural, forest and natural ecosystems (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Yang et al., 2017; Jung et al., 2018a, Jung et al., 2022, Jung et al., 2024; Brasier et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2022; Abad et al., 2023). Since the 1960s, the global number of epidemic diseases of forests and natural ecosystems caused by invasive *Phytophthora* species has increased exponentially from 5 to currently 41 (Brasier et al., 2022).

All *Phytophthora* species produce sporangia (Figures 2A, B) which usually release biflagellate zoospores (Figure 2B) or germinate directly. Aerial *Phytophthora* species spread during periods of high humidity with caducous sporangia (Figure 2B) via

rain splash, fog and wind whereas soilborne *Phytophthoras* spread during wet periods via zoospores in soil and surface water (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Chen et al., 2022). Many *Phytophthora* species form chlamydospores as vegetative survival structures (Figure 2C). Most *Phytophthora* species are characterized by the production of sexually derived enduring oospores (Figure 2D) (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Chen et al., 2022; Jung et al., 2022, Jung et al., 2024).

Generally, the management of *Phytophthora* diseases includes a wide range of measures including the prevention of pathogen introduction by using non-infested nursery stock, substrates and irrigation water, disinfecting of tools, cleaning of vehicles and boots from adhering soil particles, and phytosanitary controls using both visual inspections and high-throughput molecular detection tests; best-practice management in nurseries; avoiding of soil compaction and building of drainage systems to prevent waterlogging and flooding; application of potassium phosphite to stimulate defense reactions of roots (horticulture and forestry); fungicide applications (horticulture and agriculture); eradication via host removal and

destruction; use of nanoparticle technologies; resistance screening programs and the use of resistant host genotypes or rootstocks (horticulture, agriculture and forestry); use of effectors and NLR resistance genes; and the development and use of general models to predict regions that might be most susceptible to epidemics by certain *Phytophthora* species (e.g. *P. cinnamomi* Rands, *P. ramorum* Werres, De Cock & Man in't Veld) or regional models to predict periods with environmental conditions conducive to disease development (e.g. *P. infestans* (Mont.) de Bary) (Harris, 1991; Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Colquhoun and Hardy, 2000; Hardy, 2001; Meentemeyer et al., 2004; Rizzo et al., 2005; Robin et al., 2006; Henderson et al., 2007; Stukely et al., 2007; Frankel, 2008; Garbelotto et al., 2009; Brasier and Webber, 2010; Filipe et al., 2012; Pérez-Sierra and Jung, 2013; Crane and Shearer, 2014; Santos et al., 2017; Peterson et al., 2015; Jung et al., 2016, Jung et al., 2018a; O'Hanlon et al., 2016, O'Hanlon et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2019; Sniezko et al., 2019; González et al., 2020; Solla et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2022; Brandano et al., 2023; Martínez et al., 2023).

TABLE 8 List of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) released by *Phytophthora* sp. (A), and list of pathogen-induced plant volatiles released by *Phytophthora* sp. - infected plants (B) described in the literature.

A. Pathogen volatiles				
Pathogen	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>P. plurivora</i> ; <i>P. cactorum</i>	Acetone	67-64-1	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. plurivora</i>	α -Pinene	80-56-8	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. plurivora</i>	3-Carene	13466-78-9	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. plurivora</i>	4-Hydroxybutanoic acid	114959-05-6	2	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. plurivora</i> ; <i>P. cactorum</i>	Hexanol	111-27-3	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. plurivora</i>	Acetoin	513-86-0	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cactorum</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Dimethyl disulphide	624-92-0	2,2	Loulier et al., 2020; Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cactorum</i> ; <i>P. ramorum</i>	3-Octanone ^b	106-68-3	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cactorum</i> ; <i>P. ramorum</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. citricola</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	1-Octen-3-ol ^b	3391-86-4	1,2,2	Loulier et al., 2020; Qiu et al., 2014a; Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cactorum</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i>	Heptanol	111-70-6	1,2	Loulier et al., 2020; Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cactorum</i>	2-Pentyl furan	3777-69-3	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cactorum</i>	2-Octenol	18409-17-1	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cactorum</i>	Octanol ^b	111-87-5	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. ramorum</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Ethanol	64-17-5	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. ramorum</i>	Isoamyl alcohol ^b	123-51-3	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. ramorum</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Phenylethanol ^b	60-12-8	1,2	Loulier et al., 2020; Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. ramorum</i>	2-Methylbutanol	137-32-6	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol ^b	104-76-7	1	Loulier et al., 2020
<i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. xcambivora</i> ; <i>P. citricola</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	4-Ethyl guaiaacol ^b	2785-89-9	2, 2,2	Loulier et al., 2020; Qiu et al., 2014a; Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2,4,6-Trimethylheptane	2613-61-8	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	6-Methyl-5-hepten-2-ol	1569-60-4	2	Qiu et al., 2014a

(Continued)

TABLE 8 Continued

A. Pathogen volatiles				
Pathogen	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	6,10-Dimethyl-5,9-undecadien-2-ol	53837-34-6	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol	7786-61-0	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	5-Methyl-3-heptanone	541-85-5	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Dimethyl trisulphide	3658-80-8	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2-Butanone ^b	78-93-3	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2-Pentanone ^b	107-87-9	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Butyrolactone ^b	96-48-0	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	2-Undecanol	1653-30-1	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	cis: (Z)- β -Damascenone	59739-63-8	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i>	4-Ethylphenol ^b	123-07-9	2,2	Qiu et al., 2014a; Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	2,3-Butanediol	513-85-9	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	Hexanal	66-25-1	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. syringae</i>	2-Furanmethanol	98-00-0	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i>	2,4-Heptadienal	4313-03-5	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i>	3,5-Octadien-2-one	38284-27-4	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i>	2-Nonanol	628-99-9	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. polonica</i>	3-Nonenol	51494-28-1	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i>	2,6-Nonadienal	26370-28-5	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	Nonanol	143-08-8	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	2,4-Nonadienal	5910-87-2	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. polonica</i>	4-Decenol	57074-37-0	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	Decanol	112-30-1	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. citricola</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i> ; <i>P. syringae</i>	6-Undecen-2-one	NA	2	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	(E,Z)-2,4-Decadienal	25152-83-4	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	(E,E)-2,4-Decadienal	25152-84-5	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	3-Undecen-2-one	10522-37-9	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Methyl 2,4,6-trimethyl benzoate	2282-84-0	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. \timescambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. plurivora</i>	Decanoic acid	334-48-5	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. polonica</i>	2-Undecenal	2463-77-6	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. polonica</i>	2,4-Undecadienol	59376-58-8	2	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	Phenyl-2-hexanone	25870-62-6	2	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. gonapodyides</i>	2,6-Dodecadienal	21662-13-5	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	2-Tridecanol	1653-31-2	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	Aristolochene	26620-71-3	1	Sherwood et al., 2024

(Continued)

TABLE 8 Continued

A. Pathogen volatiles				
Pathogen	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>P. ×cambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i>	Dodecanoic acid	143-07-7	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	Tridecanol	112-70-9	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. ×cambivora</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i>	Tetradecanol	112-72-1	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	6-Pentadecen-2-one	NA	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. cinnamomi</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i> ; <i>P. multivora</i> ; <i>P. polonica</i>	γ-Dodecalactone	2305-05-7	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. ×cambivora</i> ; <i>P. gonapodyides</i>	δ-Dodecalactone	713-95-1	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>P. multivora</i>	Hexadecanol	36653-82-4	1	Sherwood et al., 2024
B. Pathogen-induced plant volatiles after <i>Phytophthora</i> sp. infection				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>Quercus robur</i> L. (seeds)	Neophytadiene isomer 2		3	Borowik et al., 2021a
<i>Quercus robur</i> (seeds)	Neophytadiene isomer 3		3	Borowik et al., 2021a
<i>Quercus robur</i> (seeds); <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> L. (seedlings)	Isoamyl alcohol	123-51-3	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001 ; Borowik et al., 2021a ; Qiu et al., 2014a
Potato (<i>Solanum tuberosum</i> L.) (tubers)	Pentanol	71-41-0	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	2-Heptanone	110-43-0	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Styrene	100-42-5	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	104-76-7	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	(E)-2-Octenal	2548-87-0	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Acetophenone	98-86-2	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Octanol	111-87-5	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Methylbenzoate	93-58-3	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Benzothiazole	95-16-9	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	3-Hydroxy-2,2-dimethyl-1-(1-methylethyl) propyl isobutyrate	18491-15-1	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-, 3-hydroxy-2,4,4-trimethylpentyl ester	74367-34-3	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Iso-caryophyllene	118-65-0	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers)	Dodecanol	112-53-8	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (tubers); Strawberry (fruit)	Nonanal	124-19-6	2,1	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001 ; Jeleń et al., 2005
Potato (tubers)	Isomenthol	23283-97-8	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Potato (leaves); Tomato (leaves)	(E)-2-Hexenal	6728-26-3	1,1	Laothawornkitkul et al., 2010 ; Li et al., 2019
Potato (leaves)	5-Ethyl-2(5H)-Furanone	2407-43-4	2	Laothawornkitkul et al., 2010
Strawberry (<i>Fragaria × ananassa</i> Duchesne) (fruit)	3-Octanone	106-68-3	1	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	o-Cymene	527-84-4	2	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	Phenylacetaldehyde	122-78-1	2	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	(Z)-Linalool oxide	1365-19-1	2	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	Pentyl benzene	538-68-1	2	Jeleń et al., 2005

(Continued)

TABLE 8 Continued

B. Pathogen-induced plant volatiles after <i>Phytophthora</i> sp. infection				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
Strawberry (fruit)	Phenethyl acetate	103-45-7	2	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	2-Undecanone	112-12-9	1	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit)	Tetradecanoic acid methyl ester	124-10-7	2	Jeleń et al., 2005
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> L.(seedlings); Potato (leaves)	Phenylethanol	60-12-8	1,2,1	Jeleń et al., 2005; Qiu et al., 2014a; Laothawornkitkul et al., 2010
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Benzyl alcohol	100-51-6	2	Jeleń et al., 2005; Qiu et al., 2014a
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	4-Ethyl guaiacol	2785-89-9	1,2	Jeleń et al., 2005; Qiu et al., 2014a
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	4-Ethylphenol	123-07-9	1,2	Jeleń et al., 2005; Qiu et al., 2014a
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Camphene	79-92-5	1,1	Jeleń et al., 2005; McCartney et al., 2018
Strawberry (fruit); <i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	1-Octen-3-ol	3391-86-4	1,1	Jeleń et al., 2005; McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (branch)	Linalool	78-70-6	1	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (branch)	(Z)-4-Hexen-1-ol	928-91-6	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (branch)	(Z)-3-Hexenyl pentanoate	35852-46-1	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Pinocarvone	30460-92-5	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Cintronellol	106-22-9	1	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	(E)- β -Caryophyllene	87-44-5	1	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	4,4-Dimethyl-3-(3-methylbut-3-enylidene)-2-methylenecyclo[4.1.0]heptane	79718-83-5	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	8,9-Dehydroneoisolongifolene	67517-14-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Calarene	17334-55-3	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	β -Vatirene	NA	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Isogermacrene D	317819-80-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Alloaromadendrene	25246-27-9	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	β -Chamigrene	18431-82-8	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	γ -Muurolene	30021-74-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	(+)- β -Selinene	17066-67-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	α -Selinene	473-13-2	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Ledene	21747-46-6	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	4,5,9,10-Dehydroisolongifolene	156747-45-4	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Caryophyllene oxide I	1139-30-6	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	(+)-Spathulenol II	6750-60-3	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Ledol	577-27-5	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Globulol	51371-47-2	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Ledene oxide	NA	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Juniper camphor	473-04-1	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Agarospinol	1460-73-7	2	McCartney et al., 2018

(Continued)

TABLE 8 Continued

B. Pathogen-induced plant volatiles after <i>Phytophthora</i> sp. infection				
Plant species	VOC name	CAS-Nr	ID level	Reference
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Sesquiterpene oxide I	NA	3	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Aristolone	6831-17-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Diterpene I	NA	3	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Diterpene II	NA	3	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Labd-14-ene	1227-93-6	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (leaf extract)	Diterpene III	NA	3	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (runoff water)	(Z)-11-Hexadecenoic acid ^a	2416-20-8	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (runoff water)	(Z)-9-Hexadecenoic acid ^a	373-49-9	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (runoff water)	Cyclic octaatomic sulfur	10544-50-0	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Rhododendron</i> hybrid (runoff water)	Oleic acid ^a	112-80-1	2	McCartney et al., 2018
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Ethyl acetate	141-78-6	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	2-Butanone	78-93-3	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Ethyl isobutyrate	97-62-1	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	2-Pentanone	107-87-9	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Ethyl 2-methylbutyrate	7452-79-1	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Butyrolactone	96-48-0	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	Benzyl alcohol	100-51-6	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> (seedlings)	4-Ethyl-1,2-dimethoxybenzene	5888-51-7	2	Qiu et al., 2014a
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (tree)	Anisole	100-66-3	2	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (tree)	Isokaurene ^a	511-85-3	2	Sherwood et al., 2024
<i>Populus</i> sp. (hybrid poplar tree)	α -Cubebene	17699-14-8	2	Durkovic et al., 2021
<i>Populus</i> sp. (hybrid poplar tree)	Germacrene D	23986-74-5	2	Durkovic et al., 2021
Potato (tubers)	Benzaldehyde	100-52-7	2	De Lacy Costello et al., 2001
Strawberry (fruit)	α -Muurelene	10208-80-7	2	Jeleń et al., 2005

^aCompound listed as VOC in the source publication but boiling point higher than 350°C.
^bIdentified in pure culture and infected plant.

The ID level reports the VOCs identification levels reported by the literature (1= identified compound, 2= putatively identified compound, based upon physicochemical properties of a chemical class and/or by spectral similarities, 3= putatively characterized compound classes, based upon characteristic physicochemical properties of a chemical class of compounds, or by spectral similarity to known compounds of a chemical class). The CAS number is a compound-specific unique identification number assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS).

Phytophthora ramorum (Figure 2B), an airborne pathogen, originates from the Laurisilva forests of East Asia (Jung et al., 2020, Jung et al., 2021). Since the early 1990s, each two lineages have been introduced to Europe (EU1 and EU2) and the Pacific Northwest (NA1 and NA2) where they became highly invasive causing leaf and shoot blights and bark cankers on a wide range of more than 100 host species, including *Rhododendron* (Figure 2E), *Camelia* and *Viburnum* spp., and the devastating epidemics “Sudden Oak Death” (California and Oregon) and “Sudden Larch Death” (UK and Republic of Ireland) which killed millions of oak, tanoak and larch trees (Werres et al., 2001; Rizzo et al., 2002; Brasier and Webber, 2010; Grünwald et al., 2012; Van Poucke et al., 2012; Harris and Webber, 2016; Jung et al., 2018a; Cobb et al., 2020). In

the EU, all *P. ramorum* lineages not yet introduced (= all lineages except of EU1) are listed as A1 quarantine pests.

The panglobal soilborne pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* (Figures 2C, D) is the most notorious and invasive member of the genus infecting and causing root rot, bark cankers (Figure 2G), dieback and mortality (Figure 2J) of more than 5000 woody plant species worldwide (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Hardham and Blackman, 2018). A recent population genomic study showed that *P. cinnamomi* originates in Southeast Asia and that the global pandemic is driven by two clonal A2 mating type lineages (Shakya et al., 2021). Besides being a major pathogen of many horticultural crops and ornamentals, *P. cinnamomi* causes some of the most devastating epidemics of forest trees and natural ecosystems

including decline and dieback of eucalypt forests across Australia; fynbos heathlands in South Africa; Valdivian rainforests and *Araucaria* forests in Chile; oak and chestnut forests in Southern Europe (Figures 2G, J) and the USA (Von Broembsen and Kruger, 1985; Shearer and Tippett, 1989; Brasier et al., 1993; Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Shearer et al., 2004; Vettraino et al., 2005; Dos Santos et al., 2011; Jung et al., 2016; Jung et al., 2018a, Jung et al., 2018b; McConnell and Balci, 2014; Sanfuentes et al., 2022).

Phytophthora cactorum (Leb. and Cohn) Schroeter is native to North America and has reached a panglobal distribution (Bourret et al., 2022). It causes both air- and soilborne diseases on a wide range of host plants including many ornamentals; forest trees like *Fagus sylvatica* L. (damping-off, root and collar rot, aerial bleeding cankers) and *Betula pendula* Roth (root and collar rot); horticultural crops like strawberries (collar rot and leather rot of fruits); and fruit trees, in particular apple trees (root, collar rot and fruit rot) (Harris, 1991; Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Jung et al., 2016, Jung et al., 2018a, Jung et al., 2019; Hantula et al., 2000; Jung, 2009; Corcobado et al., 2020).

Phytophthora plurivora Jung & Burgess originates from East Asia (Vettraino et al., 2011; Huai et al., 2013; Jung et al., 2017a, Jung et al., 2024). It is a soilborne introduced pathogen in both Europe and North America causing root and collar rot, aerial bleeding bark cankers (Figures 2F, I), and leaf and shoot blight on a wide range of woody host plants in natural ecosystems, nurseries and planting sites across; it is also one of the main drivers of current oak and beech declines across Europe (Jung, 2009; Jung and Burgess, 2009; Orlikowski et al., 2011; Reeser et al., 2011; Hansen et al., 2012; Jung et al., 2016, Jung et al., 2018a, Jung et al., 2019; Bienapfl and Balci, 2014; Brazeo et al., 2016; Corcobado et al., 2020; Frankel et al., 2020).

Phytophthora ×cambivora (Petri) Buisman (Figure 2A) is a soilborne pathogen with a cosmopolitan distribution which originates from East Asia (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Jung et al., 2017b; Mullett et al., 2023). It causes root (Figures 2H, I) and collar rot and infrequently aerial bleeding bark cankers on a wide range of woody host plants including many ornamentals, fruit trees and forest trees, and is one of the main drivers of the devastating Ink disease of sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*) in Europe and oak and beech declines across Europe (Mircetich and Matheron, 1976; Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996; Jung et al., 2000, Jung et al., 2018a, Jung et al., 2019; Vettraino et al., 2005; Jung, 2009; Corcobado et al., 2020).

6.2 Summary of literature on VOCs produced and induced by *Phytophthora* species

In this summary we focus on studies with *Phytophthora*-infection related VOCs from different *Phytophthora*-inoculated substrates i.e., chemical analyzes of VOCs directly from the pathogens or from the plants infected by *Phytophthora* species. A limited number of studies have identified and described VOCs emitted from substrates infected with *Phytophthora* species (and other oomycetes). For this work we included 12 studies, but only

two studies are focused on or include VOCs from quarantine pathogen *P. ramorum*, the target pathogen in this review.

McCartney et al. (2018), used headspace sorptive extraction (HSSE), stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) and SPME combined with GC-MS to find specific VOCs and VOC profiles from *P. ramorum*-infected *Rhododendron* hybrid 'Cunningham's White' plants. This is currently the only published study that investigates VOCs from *P. ramorum*-infected plants. For the HSSE method (*in situ* branch enclosure technique), 79 VOCs were detected. Three compounds were statistically different for *P. ramorum*-inoculated *Rhododendron* plants vs controls: linalool, (Z)-4-hexenol and (Z)-3-hexenyl pentanoate. For the SBSE liquid extraction method (leaf volatiles from a methanol extract), 115 VOCs were detected, and 31 compounds were statistically different for the inoculated *Rhododendron* plants (see Table 8). One compound, (Z)-3-hexenyl pentanoate, was produced in higher abundances in healthy plants (control) for both HSSE and SBSE. The SPME method (water runoff from the soil of potted healthy and inoculated plants), four compounds were only present in runoff water from soil infested with *P. ramorum*: (Z)-11-hexadecenoic acid, (Z)-9-hexadecenoic acid, cyclic octaatomic sulfur, oleic acid. These identified fatty acids have boiling points higher than 350°C and can be difficult to detect in ambient air except under specific experimental conditions. Loulier et al. (2020), utilized SPME/GC-MS to investigate VOCs from cultures in potato dextrose agar (PDA) of *P. ramorum*, *P. plurivora*, *P. cinnamomi*, *P. cactorum* and a range of fungi. It was found that ethanol was shared between *P. ramorum* and *P. cinnamomi* (see Table 8). Other VOCs detected (but also present in various species of fungi) were 3-octanone, 1-octen-3-ol, 2-methylbutanol and isoamyl alcohol from *P. ramorum*. *P. ramorum* also emitted 2-phenylethanol. Loulier et al. (2020) further found that *P. ramorum* emitted higher amounts of compounds compared to the other *Phytophthora* species, and this was also confirmed in an analysis using an e-nose instrument developed in the same study. The e-nose could discriminate between VOCs emitted by *P. ramorum*, *Fusarium poae* (Peck) Wollenweber, *Trichoderma asperellum* Samuels, Lieckfeldt & Nirenberg and *Rhizoctonia solani* (Prillieux & Delacroix) Donk. Interestingly, *P. plurivora* emitted two monoterpenes α -pinene and 3-carene. Furthermore, Loulier et al. (2020) found that a major difference between the *Phytophthora* species and the fungi could be the amount of sesquiterpene produced, where the *Phytophthora* tested does not release these compounds/VOCs, but all tested fungal species did (except one). A recent study by Sherwood et al. (2024) used SPME/GC-MS to analyze the volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted by eight *Phytophthora* species cultivated on medium: *P. cambivora*, *P. cinnamomi*, *P. citricola*, *P. gonapodyides*, *P. multivora*, *P. plurivora*, *P. polonica*, and *P. syringae*. A total of 58 compounds were identified. However, identification from mass spectral libraries was not possible for some compounds, and these were excluded from Table 8. Surprisingly, there was very little overlap with the VOCs identified in the Loulier et al. (2020), sharing only three VOCs: 1-octen-3-ol, heptanol, and 4-ethyl guaiacol. Additionally, the sesquiterpene aristolochene was identified in *P. cinnamomi*, which contradicts Loulier et al. (2020)'s results. Some

Phytophthora species may lack some genes for terpene biosynthesis (Chen et al., 2016), limiting their ability to produce a diverse range of terpenes compared to fungal organisms.

Qiu et al., 2014a; Qiu et al., 2014b optimized and used SPME to find specific VOCs from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. After inoculation of different substrates [V8A, PDA, lupin seedlings (*Lupinus angustifolius* L. 'Danja'), soil, and soil + lupin seedlings] with *P. cinnamomi*, this study identified 87 VOCs from infected and non-infected substrate. Four of these, 4-ethyl guaiacol (4-ethyl-2-methoxy phenol), 4-ethylphenol, butyrolactone, and phenylethanol, were significant and specific for *P. cinnamomi*-infections. This study shows that it is possible to detect differences between inoculated and non-inoculated plants and substrates. Borowik et al. (2021a) used SPME and found specific VOCs for *P. plurivora* and *Pythium intermedium* (de Bary) Uzuhashi, Tojo & Kakishima from *in vitro* infected germinated acorns of *Quercus robur* L. In total, four VOCs were detected on the inoculated acorns, which were not found in the control acorns. Three of them, neophytadiene isomer 2, neophytadiene isomer 3 and isoamyl alcohol were significant and specific for acorns infected with *P. plurivora*, whereas methylcarveol were specific for *Pythium intermedium*-infected acorns. Furthermore, Borowik et al. (2021b) also developed a low-cost electronic nose that applies six non-specific Figaro Inc. metal oxide sensors. A machine learning approach with this system was able to distinguish between *P. plurivora* and *Pythium intermedium* grown on Petri dishes with V8-Agar media (Borowik et al., 2021b) and using *in vitro* infected germinated acorns of *Q. robur* (Borowik et al., 2021a). Durkovic et al. (2021) used HS/GC-MS to analyze emissions from field-grown hybrid poplar infected with *P. cactorum* and *P. plurivora*. Their findings showed that the emissions of both sesquiterpenes, α -cubebene and germacrene D, were induced solely by the *Phytophthora* inoculations (both species).

De Lacy Costello et al. (2001) used improvised thermal desorption system (sorbent Tenax TA, Tenax GR and Carbosieve III) for *P. infestans*- and *Fusarium coeruleum* Libert ex Saccardo inoculated potato tubers (*Solanum tuberosum* L. cv. Maris Piper). The four most abundant and significant VOCs were common for both pathogens, but not present in the control: benzothiazole, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethyl-1-(1-methylethyl)propyl isobutyrate and propanoic acid, 2-methyl-, 3-hydroxy-2,4,4-trimethylpentyl ester (see Table 8). Laothawornkitkul et al. (2010) detected three VOCs specific for *P. infestans*-infected potato leaves: 5-ethyl-2(5H)-furanone, (*E*)-2-hexenal, and phenylethanol (VOCs were trapped on volatile traps (Tenax sorbent) and then eluted with a solvent). Even though both studies on potato used similar technology the experimental conditions, potato growth stage and variety differed could explain the difference in the VOCs emitted from *P. infestans*-infected potato. Li et al. (2019), developed a smartphone-based VOC fingerprinting platform that could detect *P. infestans* in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. They suggest that (*E*)-2-hexenal is a major diagnostic VOC marker for *P. infestans* infection, which aligns with the findings of an earlier study by Laothawornkitkul et al. (2010). However, Xu et al. (2021) later demonstrated that (*E*)-2-hexenal is involved in *Botrytis cinerea* infection in tomato plants.

Jeleń et al., 2005 used SPME/GC-MS to find specific VOCs for *P. cactorum*-infected strawberries (*Fragaria × ananassa* (Duchesne ex Weston) Duchesne ex Rozier). Of 160 VOCs, 17 compounds were specific for inoculated strawberries and were absent in non-inoculated strawberries. Of these VOCs, two were found to be causing the characteristic off-odor from *P. cactorum*-infected strawberries (using gas chromatography-olfactometry): 4-ethylphenol and 4-ethyl guaiacol.

Each of these studies found different VOCs and different VOC profiles obtained from the different *Phytophthora* species-infected substrates, indicating there are *Phytophthora* species-specific VOCs and VOC profiles. Hence, enabling the development of e-noses for aiding detection of these pathogens, especially those of quarantine status and high destructive potential. However, of the above referenced papers, only twelve species of oomycetes (*P. cactorum*, *P. cinnamomi*, *P. infestans*, *P. ramorum*, *P. plurivora*, *P. cambivora*, *P. citricola*, *P. gonapodyides*, *P. multivora*, *P. polonica*, *P. syringae* and *Pythium intermedium*) have been investigated so far and they have utilized several different infected substrates and various methods to collect VOCs from the pathogens themselves or the infected plants. The VOC information for *Phytophthora* is very scarce compared to other pests such as the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*, the brown marmorated stink bug *Halyomorpha halys* or the cotton Boll worm *Helicoverpa armigera*. It is not yet possible for any *Phytophthora* species to find a VOC profile that is robustly produced in connection with the target organisms i.e., VOCs that are not only produced in one infected plant variety or under one certain temperature/light regime. Three VOCs were consistently identified in at least three independent studies of *Phytophthora*: 1-octen-3-ol, 4-ethylguaiacol, and phenylethanol (see Table 8). However, a limitation of these potential biomarkers is that they are also produced by several other organism.

Finding suitable VOCs for the early detection of *Phytophthora* in woody plants is challenging. The genus *Phytophthora* often lacks genes necessary for the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites which are commonly used for fungal detection. This could be potentially utilized. Research by Loulier et al. (2020) using electronic noses (E-noses) demonstrates that the detection of specific terpenes can potentially distinguish between fungal infections and *Phytophthora* infections. Another challenge is that a significant portion of the pathogen resides within the roots, unlike infections caused by organisms like *P. infestans*. For the latter, a simpler device for VOC collection was successfully developed (Li et al., 2019). To capture sufficient VOCs for future analysis from this root-dwelling pathogen, a more sensitive method of collection and analysis, such as TD-GC-MS, is recommended.

6.3 Candidate VOCs for *Phytophthora ramorum* detection

Since only two studies included VOCs from *P. ramorum*, either *P. ramorum*-infected plants (McCartney et al., 2018) or from the pathogen in culture (Loulier et al., 2020), it is not possible to select any robust candidate VOCs for this pathogen. Therefore, all current

VOCs that do not appear in the controls in these studies are listed as *P. ramorum* candidate VOCs in Table 8. More VOC profiling of *P. ramorum* and other *Phytophthora* species and *Phytophthora*-infected plants are urgently needed to find functioning candidate VOCs for these pathogens.

7 Discussion

Exploiting VOCs released by the pests and infested plants has shown to be a promising approach to assess the presence of quarantine organisms (MacDougall et al., 2022). Our review, however, highlights how crucial it is to have clear target signature VOCs for prompt and accurate pest detection. Volatiles specific to the organism (in case of insect, the pheromones) and herbivore-induced plant volatiles clearly appear as reliable VOCs for pest detection and identification. In the three insects we considered, at least one candidate compound was found among aggregation, defense, alarm, sexual and oviposition deterrent pheromones. No specific volatile has yet been identified for the nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* and for the oomycete *Phytophthora ramorum*.

Among the five organisms we analyzed, the insect pheromones appeared to be the most reliable candidates. Although the specificity of insect pheromones is geared toward precise communication within a species, the generalization and quantities of HIPVs released by plants serves a broader ecological context, influencing a wide array of interactions within an ecosystem (Shivaramu et al., 2017). In the case of insect pheromones, the specificity is often a result of coevolution between the emitter and the receiver within the same species. The accuracy of the signal is crucial for reproductive success. On the other hand, the generalization of HIPVs in plants is likely to be a strategy to maximize the benefits of indirect defense against herbivores and to establish complex ecological relationships with various organisms in the environment. For a precise detection through VOCs to be effective and applicable, pest-specific signals independent of the plant species should be desirable, pheromones satisfy this requirement more than HIPVs. Pheromones present, however, limitations. Since pheromones primary function is to deliver precise information within the species only at specific time periods, they are not constantly emitted. For instance, *H. halys* does not release defensive odors if not disturbed (Nixon et al., 2018), and the aggregation pheromone is emitted by males only (Weber et al., 2017). In *Spodoptera frugiperda* only adult virgin females emit the sexual pheromone. Therefore, eggs and immature insect stages would not be identified based on the pheromones that we currently know about. In contrast, the oviposition deterrent pheromones in *Helicoverpa armigera* are not only produced by females after oviposition, but also by eggs and larval frass (Guoqing et al., 2001; Xu et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2008), making them a more reliable VOCs for pest identification. It is highly desirable that similar compounds would be found for other insect species.

The HIPVs described in this review may have limitations as candidates in the case of *H. halys* and *S. frugiperda*. In *H. halys*, the HIPVs are different depending on plant species, and no apparent

common VOC was released following *H. halys* damage. In the case of maize plants infested with different species of the genus *Spodoptera*, the HIPV blends lack unique molecules that could identify the attacking species. However, there are consistent difference in ratios that could provide such information. Further research is needed to determine consistencies and specificities in host plant responses to determine reliable combinations of compounds as candidates of pest identification.

A more favorable situation emerged in the HIPVs of *H. armigera*. Four terpenoids were found to be specific to CBW infestation of maize plants, among which β -myrcene was found in cotton too, and D-limonene also in French bean and tomato. β -Pinene was common in maize, cotton, tobacco, and tomato. Specificity and consistency allowed to select these HIPVs as candidates for the CBW detection, also showing that the use of HIPVs as identification cues is possible.

The use of HIPVs as marker signals should be considered carefully, because of the complexity that emerges from real-life conditions. Pest surveillance usually applies to international trade, and plant might face long and stressful journeys. Abiotic stress factors, such as drought, temperature extremes, and nutrient deficiencies, can vary widely in intensity and duration. The plant volatilome responses to such stressors must be considered when targeting for specific VOCs. In an extensive review, Loreto and Schnitzler (2010) reported how abiotic stresses enhance biogenic VOC emission rates and patterns, and how these stressors can alter the constitutive VOCs, causing them to either increase or decrease in emission, or they can cause the synthesis of new VOCs and suppression of others. The capacity of discerning HIPVs from abiotic stress-related plant VOCs becomes crucial. More data are needed to get a full picture of the diversity of plant responses under different stress combinations.

In case of the nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, the scarce literature available did not provide any robust data to allow the selection of candidate VOCs. The few compounds mentioned are common terpenoids that lack consistency between the pine species and are thus unreliable. A considerable effort is required to expand the information available on the *B. xylophilus*-induced plant volatiles. Similarly, the number of studies on *Phytophthora ramorum* did not provide enough evidence to confidently select signature VOCs. Only one research paper (Loulier et al., 2020) analyzed the volatiles released by a pure *P. ramorum* culture, and another one (McCartney et al., 2018) from infected hybrid *Rhododendron* plants. As for the nematode, the need to expand the literature on the subject is essential.

8 Conclusions

This review collected and analyzed the available literature concerning pest VOCs and pest-induced VOCs from five selected pests/pathogens relevant to the international pest surveillance programs. The aim was to select the pest signature volatiles that can be employed in specific volatile detection. The picture that

appears shows that insects pheromones are reliable indicators of the pest presence, albeit with limitations. The use of induced plant VOCs is a viable solution but requires in depth exploration that takes into account the complexity of the plant response to abiotic and biotic factors. As the development of volatiles-based approaches are advancing, their use is increasingly seen as a viable solution for early pest detection. It is imperative to increase the number of studies and the quality of information available on the most crucial pest species. The research in this direction should be methodical, precise and rigorous, aiming at offering a broad database of volatiles signatures.

Author contributions

RF: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. MP: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. GT: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. CA: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. MI: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. TT: Writing – review & editing. JF: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. TJ: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. DB: Writing – review & editing. AP: Writing – review & editing. SA: Writing – review & editing. LC: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. MB: Writing – review & editing.

References

- Abad, Z. G., Burgess, T. I., Bourret, T., Bensch, K., Cacciola, S., Scanu, B., et al. (2023). *Phytophthora*: taxonomic and phylogenetic revision of the genus. *Stud. Mycology* 106, 259–348. doi: 10.3114/sim.2023.106.05
- Abelleira, A., Picoaga, A., Mansilla, J. P., and Aguin, O. (2011). Detection of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, Causal Agent of Pine Wilt Disease on *Pinus Pinaster* in Northwestern Spain. *Plant Dis.* 95, 776–776. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-12-10-0902
- Abram, P. K., Talamas, E. J., Acheampong, S., Mason, P. G., and Garipey, T. D. (2019). First detection of the samurai wasp, *Trissolcus japonicus* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae), in Canada. *J. Hymenoptera Res.* 68, 29–36. doi: 10.3897/jhr.68.32203
- Abro, Z., Kimathi, E., De Groot, H., Tefera, T., Sevgan, S., Niassy, S., et al. (2021). Socioeconomic and health impacts of fall armyworm in Ethiopia. *PLoS One* 16, e0257736. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0257736
- Akhoundi, M., Chebbah, D., Elissa, N., Brun, S., Jan, J., Lacaze, I., et al. (2023). Volatile organic compounds: A promising tool for bed bug detection. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 20, 5214. doi: 10.3390/ijerph20065214
- Alborn, H. T., Turlings, T. C. J., Jones, T. H., Stenhagen, G., Loughrin, J. H., and Tumlinson, J. H. (1997). An elicitor of plant volatiles from beet armyworm oral secretion. *Science* 276, 945–949. doi: 10.1126/science.276.5314.945
- Aldrich, J. R., Oliver, J. E., Lusby, W. R., Kochansky, J. P., and Lockwood, J. A. (1987). Pheromone strains of the cosmopolitan pest, *Nezara viridula* (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae). *J. Exp. Zoology* 244, 171–175. doi: 10.1002/jez.1402440121
- Andrade, R., Rodriguez, C., and Oechslslager, A. C. (2000). Optimization of a pheromone lure for *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith) in Central America. *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.* 11, 609–613. doi: 10.1590/S0103-50532000000600009
- Babendreier, D., Koku Agboyi, L., Beseh, P., Osae, M., Nboyine, J., Ofori, S. E. K., et al. (2020). The efficacy of alternative, environmentally friendly plant protection measures for control of fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, in maize. *Insects* 11, 240, 1–21. doi: 10.3390/insects11040240
- Back, M. A., Bonifácio, L., Inácio, M. L., Mota, M., and Boa, E. (2024). Pine wilt disease: A global threat to forestry. *Plant Pathol.* 73, 1026–1041. doi: 10.1111/ppa.13875
- Baldwin, I. T. (2010). Plant volatiles. *Curr. Biol.* 20, R392–R397. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2010.02.052
- Batista-Pereira, L. G., Stein, K., de Paula, A. F., Moreira, J. A., Cruz, I., Figueiredo, M. D. L. C., et al. (2006). Isolation, identification, synthesis, and field evaluation of the sex pheromone of the Brazilian population of *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 32, 1085–1099. doi: 10.1007/s10886-006-9048-5
- Baudron, F., Zaman-Allah, M. A., Chaipa, I., Chari, N., and Chinwada, P. (2019). Understanding the factors influencing fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda* J.E. Smith) damage in African smallholder maize fields and quantifying its impact on yield. A case study in Eastern Zimbabwe. *Crop Prot.* 120, 141–150. doi: 10.1016/j.cropro.2019.01.028
- Behere, G. T., Tay, W. T., Russell, D. A., Kranthi, K. R., and Batterham, P. (2013). Population genetic structure of cotton bollworm *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepitoptera: Noctuidae) in India as inferred from EPIC-PCR DNA markers. *PLoS One* 8, e53448. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0053448
- Bi, Z., Gong, Y., Huang, X., Yu, H., Bai, L., and Hu, J. (2015). Efficacy of four nematicides against the reproduction and development of pinewood nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. *J. Nematol.* 47, 126–132.
- Bienapfl, J. C., and Balci, Y. (2014). Movement of *Phytophthora* spp. in Maryland's nursery trade. *Plant Dis.* 98, 134–144. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-06-13-0662-RE
- Blaauw, B. R., Polk, D., and Nielsen, A. L. (2015). IPM-CPR for peaches: incorporating behaviorally-based methods to manage *Halyomorpha halys* and key pests in peach. *Pest Manage. Sci.* 71, 1513–1522. doi: 10.1002/ps.2015.71.issue-11
- Borges, M., Jepson, P. C., and Howse, P. E. (1987). Long-range mate location and close-range courtship behaviour of the green stink bug, *Nezara viridula* and its mediation by sex pheromones. *Entomologia Experimentalis Applicata* 44, 205–212. doi: 10.1111/j.1570-7458.1987.tb00546.x
- Borowik, P., Adamowicz, L., Tarakowski, R., Waclawik, P., Oszako, T., Ślusarski, S., et al. (2021b). Application of a low-cost electronic nose for differentiation between pathogenic oomycetes *Pythium intermedium* and *Phytophthora plurivora*. *Sensors* 21, 1326. doi: 10.3390/s21041326
- Borowik, P., Adamowicz, L., Tarakowski, R., Waclawik, P., Oszako, T., Ślusarski, S., et al. (2021a). Electronic nose differentiation between *Quercus robur* acorns infected by pathogenic oomycetes *Phytophthora plurivora* and *Pythium intermedium*. *Molecules* 26, 5272. doi: 10.3390/molecules26175272

Funding

The author(s) declare financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. This research was funded by the project PurPest, grant number 101060634 supported under HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-04-Tackling outbreaks of plant pests, funded under the HORIZON Research and Innovation Action (RIA) from the European Research Executive Agency (REA)-Green Europe REA.B.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Publisher's note

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers. Any product that may be evaluated in this article, or claim that may be made by its manufacturer, is not guaranteed or endorsed by the publisher.

- Bos, L. D., Sterk, P. J., and Schultz, M. J. (2013). Volatile metabolites of pathogens: a systematic review. *PLoS Pathog.* 9, e1003311. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1003311
- Bourret, T. B., Fajardo, S. N., Engert, C. P., and Rizzo, D. M. (2022). A barcode-based phylogenetic characterization of *Phytophthora cactorum* identifies two cosmopolitan lineages with distinct host affinities and the first report of *Phytophthora pseudotsugae* in California. *J. Fungi* 8, 303. doi: 10.3390/jof8030303
- Brandano, A., Serra, S., Hardy, G. E. S. J., and Scanu, B. (2023). Potassium phosphonate induces resistance in sweet chestnut against ink disease caused by *Phytophthora* species. *Pathogens* 12, 365. doi: 10.3390/pathogens12030365
- Brasier, C. M., Robredo, F., and Ferraz, J. F. P. (1993). Evidence for *Phytophthora cinnamomi* involvement in Iberian oak decline. *Plant Pathol.* 42, 140–145. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3059.1993.tb01482.x
- Brasier, C., Scanu, B., Cooke, D., and Jung, T. (2022). *Phytophthora*: an ancient, historic, biologically and structurally cohesive and evolutionarily successful generic concept in need of preservation. *IMA Fungus* 13, 12. doi: 10.1186/s43008-022-00097-z
- Brasier, C. M., and Webber, J. (2010). Sudden larch death. *Nature* 466, 824–825. doi: 10.1038/466824a
- Braze, N. J., Wick, R. L., and Hulvey, J. P. (2016). *Phytophthora* species recovered from the Connecticut River Valley in Massachusetts, USA. *Mycologia*, 108, 6–19doi: 10.3852/15-038
- Brezolin, A. N., Martinazzo, J., Muenchen, D. K., de Cezaro, A. M., Rigo, A. A., Steffens, C., et al. (2018). Tools for detecting insect semiochemicals: a review. *Analytical Bioanalytical Chem.* 410, 4091–4108. doi: 10.1007/s00216-018-1118-3
- Calam, D. H., and Youdeowei, A. (1968). Identification and functions of secretion from the posterior scent gland of fifth instar larva of the bug *Dysdercus intermedius*. *J. Insect Physiol.* 14, 1147–1158. doi: 10.1016/0022-1910(68)90054-1
- Candian, V., Pansa, M. G., Santoro, K., Spadaro, D., Tavella, L., and Tedeschi, R. (2020). Photosensitive exclusion netting in apple orchards: Effectiveness against pests and impact on beneficial arthropods, fungal diseases and fruit quality. *Pest Manage. Sci.* 76, 179–187. doi: 10.1002/ps.v76.1
- Carnio, V., Favaro, R., Preti, M., and Angeli, S. (2024). Impact of Aggregation Pheromone Traps on Spatial Distribution of *Halyomorpha halys* Damage in Apple Orchards. *Insects* 15, 791. doi: 10.3390/insects15100791
- Carrasquinho, I., Lisboa, A., Inácio, M. L., and Gonçalves, E. (2018). Genetic variation in susceptibility to pine wilt disease of maritime pine (*Pinus Pinaster* Aiton) half-sib families. *Ann. For. Sci.* 75, 85. doi: 10.1007/s13595-018-0759-x
- Carroll, M. J., Schmelz, E. A., Meagher, R. L., et al. (2006). Attraction of spodoptera frugiperda larvae to volatiles from herbivore-damaged maize seedlings. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 32, 1911–1924. doi: 10.1007/s10886-006-9117-9
- Chen, Q., Bakhshi, M., Balci, Y., Broders, K. D., Cheewangkoon, R., Chen, S. F., et al. (2022). Genera of phytopathogenic fungi: GOPHY 4. *Stud. Mycology* 101, 417–564. doi: 10.3114/sim.2022.101.06
- Chen, X., Köllner, T. G., Jia, Q., Norris, A., Santhanam, B., Rabe, P., et al. (2016). Terpene synthase genes in eukaryotes beyond plants and fungi: Occurrence in social amoebae. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 113, 12132–12137. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1610379113
- Chu, L., Deng, S., Zhao, R., Deng, J., and Kang, X. (2016). Comparison of adsorption/desorption of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) on electrospun nanofibers with tenax TA for potential application in sampling. *PLoS One* 11, e0163388. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0163388
- Cobb, R. C., Haas, S. E., Kruskamp, N., Dillon, W. W., Swiecki, T. J., Rizzo, D. M., et al. (2020). The magnitude of regional-scale tree mortality caused by the invasive pathogen *Phytophthora ramorum*. *Earth's Future* 8, e2020EF001500. doi: 10.1029/2020EF001500
- Cock, M. J. W., Beseh, P. K., Buddie, A. G., Cafá, G., and Crozier, J. (2017). Molecular methods to detect *Spodoptera frugiperda* in Ghana, and implications for monitoring the spread of invasive species in developing countries. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 4103. doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-04238-y
- Colquhoun, I. J., and Hardy, G. E. S. J. (2000). Managing the risks of *Phytophthora* root and collar rot during bauxite mining in the *Eucalyptus marginata* (Jarrah) forest of Western Australia. *Plant Dis.* 84, 116–127. doi: 10.1094/PDIS.2000.84.2.116
- Corcobado, T., Cech, T. L., Brandstetter, M., Daxer, A., Hüttler, C., Kudláček, T., et al. (2020). Decline of European beech in Austria: involvement of *Phytophthora* spp. and contributing biotic and abiotic factors. *Forests* 11, 895. doi: 10.3390/f11080895
- Costi, E., Haye, T., and Maistrello, L. (2017). Biological parameters of the invasive brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, in Southern Europe. *J. Pest Sci.* 90, 1059–1067. doi: 10.1007/s10340-017-0899-z
- Crane, C. E., and Shearer, B. L. (2014). Comparison of phosphite application methods for control of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in threatened communities. *Australas. Plant Pathol.* 43, 143–149. doi: 10.1007/s13313-013-0260-9
- Cruz-Esteban, S., Rojas, J. C., Sánchez-Guillén, D., Cruz-López, L., and Malo, E. (2018). Geographic variation in pheromone component ratio and antennal responses, but not in attraction, to sex pheromones among fall armyworm populations infesting corn in Mexico. *J. Pest Sci.* 91, 973–983. doi: 10.1007/s10340-018-0967-z
- Cui, S., Ling, P., Zhu, H., and Keener, H. M. (2018). Plant pest detection using an artificial nose system: A review. *Sensors* 18, 378. doi: 10.3390/s18020378
- Cunningham, J. P., and Zalucki, M. P. (2014). Understanding heliothine (Lepidoptera: Heliothinae) pests: What is a host plant? *J. Economic Entomology* 107, 881–896. doi: 10.1603/EC14036
- Cunningham, J. P., Zalucki, M. P., and West, S. A. (1999). Learning in *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae): A new look at the behaviour and control of a polyphagous pest. *Bull. Entomological Res.* 89, 201–207. doi: 10.1017/S0007485399000310
- Day, R., Abrahams, P., Bateman, M., Beale, T., Clotey, V., Cock, M., et al. (2017). Fall armyworm: Impacts and implications for Africa. *Outlooks Pest Manage.* 28, 196–201. doi: 10.1564/v28_oct_02
- Degen, T., Dillmann, C., Marion-Poll, F., and Turlings, T. C. J. (2004). Genetic variability in herbivore-induced volatile emission within a broad range of maize inbred lines. *Plant Physiol.* 135, 1928–1938. doi: 10.1104/pp.104.039891
- De Groote, H., Kimenju, S. C., Munyua, B., Palmas, S., Kassie, M., and Bruce, A. (2020). Spread and impact of fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda* JE Smith) in maize production areas of Kenya. *Agriculture Ecosyst. Environ.* 292, 106804. doi: 10.1016/j.agee.2019.106804
- De Lacy Costello, B. P. J., Evans, P., Ewen, R. J., Gunson, H., Ratcliffe, N., and Spencer-Phillips, P. (2001). GC-MS analyses of volatile organic compounds from potato tubers inoculated with *Phytophthora infestans* or *Fusarium coeruleum*. *Plant Pathol.* 50, 489–496. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-3059.2001.00594.x
- De la Fuente, B., Saura, S., and Beck, P. S. (2018). Predicting the spread of an invasive tree pest: the pine wood nematode in Southern Europe. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 55, 2374–2385. doi: 10.1111/jpe.2018.55.issue-5
- De Lange, E., Laplante, D., Guo, H., Xu, W., Vlimant, M., Erb, M., et al. (2020). *Spodoptera frugiperda* caterpillars suppress herbivore-induced volatile emissions in maize. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 46, 344–360. doi: 10.1007/s10886-020-01153-x
- de Lange, E. S., Farnier, K., Gaudillat, B., et al. (2016). Comparing the attraction of two parasitoids to herbivore-induced volatiles of maize and its wild ancestors, the teosintes. *Chemoecology* 26, 33–44. doi: 10.1007/s00049-015-0205-6
- Descouins, C., Silvain, J. F., Lalanne-Cassou, B., and Cheron, H. (1988). Monitoring of crop pests by sexual trapping of males in Guadeloupe and Guyana. *Agriculture Ecosyst. Environ.* 21, 53–56. doi: 10.1016/0167-8809(88)90139-9
- Dicke, M., Van Loon, J. J., and Soler, R. (2009). Chemical complexity of volatiles from plants induced by multiple attack. *Nat. Chem. Biol.* 5, 317–324. doi: 10.1038/nchembio.169
- Dos Santos, A., Tessmann, D. J., Alves, T. C. A., Vida, J. B., and Harakava, R. (2011). Root and crown rot of Brazilian Pine (*Araucaria angustifolia*) caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi**. *J. Phytopathol.* 159, 194–196. doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0434.2010.01741.x
- Downes, S., Kriticos, D., Parry, H., Paull, C., Schellhorn, N., and Zalucki, M. P. (2016). A perspective on management of *Helicoverpa armigera*: transgenic Bt cotton, IPM, and landscape. *Pest Manage. Sci.* 73, 485–492. doi: 10.1002/ps.4461
- Durkovic, J., Bubeniková, T., Gužmerová, A., Fleischer, P., Kurjak, D., Čanová, I., et al. (2021). Effects of *Phytophthora* inoculations on photosynthetic behaviour and induced defence responses of plant volatiles in field-grown hybrid poplar tolerant to bark canker disease. *J. Fungi* 7, 969. doi: 10.3390/jof7110969
- EPP0 (2023). EPP0 standard on diagnostics - PM 7/44(4) *bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. *EPP0 Bull.* 53, 156–183. doi: 10.1111/epp.12915
- Erwin, D. C., and Ribeiro, O. K. (1996). *Phytophthora diseases worldwide* (St. Paul, Minnesota: APS Press).
- Eschen, R., Beale, T., Bonnini, J. M., Constantine, K. L., Duah, S., Finch, E. A., et al. (2021). Towards estimating the economic cost of invasive alien species to African crop and livestock production. *CABI Agric. Bioscience* 2, 1–18. doi: 10.1186/s43170-021-00038-7
- European Commission (2020). “A farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system.” in *COM 2020 381 final* (European Commission, Brussels). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0381>.
- Falugiarda, M., Carnio, V., Chiesa, S. G., Pignalosa, A., Anfora, G., Angeli, G., et al. (2023). Factors influencing short-term parasitoid establishment and efficacy for the biological control of *Halyomorpha halys* with the samurai wasp *Trissolcus japonicus*. *Pest Manage. Sci.* 79 (7), 2397–2414. doi: 10.1002/ps.7423
- FAO (2020). “The global action for fall armyworm control: Action framework 2020–2022,” in *Working together to tame the global threat* (FAO, Rome), 50.
- Fennine, C., Favaro, R., Khomenko, I., Biasioli, F., Cappellin, L., and Angeli, S. (2024). Diel rhythm of volatile emissions from males and females of the olive fruit fly *Bactrocera oleae* using PTR-ToF and GC-MS. *J. Insect Physiol.* 153, 104596. doi: 10.1016/j.jinsphys.2023.104596
- Filipe, J. A. N., Cobb, R. C., Meentemeyer, R. K., Lee, C. A., Valachovic, Y. S., Cook, A. R., et al. (2012). Landscape epidemiology and control of pathogens with cryptic and long-distance dispersal: Sudden Oak Death in Northern Californian forests. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 8, e1002328. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002328
- Firake, D. M., and Behere, G. T. (2020). Natural mortality of invasive fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (JE Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in maize agroecosystems of northeast India. *Biol. Control* 148, 104303. doi: 10.1016/j.biocontrol.2020.104303
- Fleischer, S. J., Harding, C. L., Blom, P. F., White, J., and Grehan, J. (2005). *Spodoptera frugiperda* pheromone lures to avoid nontarget captures of *Leucania phragmatidicola*. *J. Economic Entomology* 98, 66–71. doi: 10.1093/jees/98.1.66
- Fonseca, L., Cardoso, J. M. S., Lopes, A., Pestana, M., Abreu, F., Nunes, N., et al. (2012). The pinewood nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, in Madeira Island. *Helminthologia*. doi: 10.2478/s11687-012-0020-3
- Fornasiero, D., Scaccini, D., Lombardo, V., Galli, G., and Pozzebon, A. (2023). Effect of exclusion net timing of deployment and color on *Halyomorpha halys* (Hemiptera:

- Pentatomidae) infestation in pear and apple orchards. *Crop Prot.* 172, 106–331. doi: 10.1016/j.cpro.2023.106331
- Fraga, D. F., Parker, J., Busoli, A. C., Hamilton, G. C., Nielsen, A. L., and Rodriguez-Saona, C. (2017). Behavioral responses of predaceous minute pirate bugs to tridecane, a volatile emitted by the brown marmorated stink bug. *J. Pest Sci.* 90, 1107–1118. doi: 10.1007/s10340-016-0825-9
- Frankel, S. J. (2008). Sudden oak death and *Phytophthora ramorum* in the USA: a management challenge. *Australas. Plant Pathol.* 37, 19–25. doi: 10.1071/AP07088
- Frankel, S. J., Conforti, C., Hillman, J., Ingolia, M., Benner, D., Alexander, J. M., et al. (2020). *Phytophthora* introductions in restoration areas: Responding to protect California native flora from human-assisted pathogen spread. *Forests* 11, 1291. doi: 10.3390/f11121291
- Fundurulic, A., Faria, J. M., and Inácio, M. L. (2023). Advances in electronic nose sensors for plant disease and pest detection. *Eng. Proc.* 48, 14. doi: 10.3390/CSAC2023-14890
- Futai, K. (2008). "Pine wilt in Japan: From first incidence to the present," in *Pine wilt disease*. Eds. B. G. Zhao, K. Futai, J. R. Sutherland and Y. Takeuchi (Springer, Tokyo), 5–12.
- Futai, K. (2013). Pine wood nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 51, 61–83. doi: 10.1146/annurev-phyto-081211-172910
- Garbelotto, M., Harnik, T. Y., and Schmidt, D. J. (2009). Efficacy of phosphonic acid, metalaxyl-M and copper hydroxide against *Phytophthora ramorum* in vitro and in planta. *Plant Pathol.* 58, 111–119. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3059.2008.01894.x
- Gaspar, M. C., Agostinho, B., Fonseca, L., Abrantes, I., de Sousa, H. C., and Braga, M. E. M. (2020). Impact of the pinewood nematode on naturally-emitted volatiles and scCO₂ extracts from *Pinus pinaster* branches: a comparison with *P. pinea*. *J. Supercritical Fluids* 159, 104784. doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2020.104784
- Gebrezihier, H. G. (2018). The role of herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) as indirect plant defense mechanisms in a diverse plant and herbivore species; a review. *Int. J. Agriculture Environ. Food Sci.* 2, 139–147. doi: 10.31015/jaefs.18024
- Gebrezihier, H. G., and Nakamura, K. (2016). Responses of a predatory bug to a mixture of herbivore-induced plant volatiles from multiple plant species. *Arthropod-Plant Interact.* 10, 429–444. doi: 10.1007/s11829-016-9456-6
- González, M., Romero, M.-A., Serrano, M.-S., and Sánchez, M.-E. (2020). Fosetylaluminum injection controls root rot disease affecting *Quercus suber* in southern Spain. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 156, 101–109. doi: 10.1007/s10658-019-01865-1
- Gouinguéné, S., Alborn, H., and Turlings, T. C. J. (2003). Induction of volatile emissions in maize by different larval instars of *Spodoptera littoralis*. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 29, 145–162. doi: 10.1023/A:1021984715420
- Gouinguéné, S., and Turlings, T. C. J. (2002). The effects of abiotic factors on induced volatile emissions in corn plants. *Plant Physiol.* 129, 1296–1307. doi: 10.1104/pp.001941
- Groot, A. T., Marr, M., Schöfl, G., Lorenz, S., Svatos, A., and Heckel, D. G. (2008). Host strain specific sex pheromone variation in *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *Front. Zoology* 5, 20. doi: 10.1186/1742-9994-5-20
- Grünwald, N. J., Garbelotto, M., Goss, E. M., Heungens, K., and Prospero, S. (2012). Emergence of the Sudden Oak Death pathogen *Phytophthora ramorum*. *Trends Microbiol.* 20, 131–138. doi: 10.1016/j.tim.2011.12.006
- Gullan, P. J., and Cranston, P. S. (2014). *The insects: an outline of entomology* (Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons).
- Guo, G. J., Zhao Jianzhou, Z. J., He Kanglai, H. K., Zhang Feng, Z. F., and Wang Zhenying, W. Z. (2018). Potential invasion of the crop-devastating insect pest fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* to China. *Plant Prot.* 44, 1–10. doi: 10.16688/j.zwbh.2018452
- Guoqing, L., Zhaojun, H., Lili, M., Xiaoran, Q., Changkun, C., and Yinchang, W. (2001). Natural oviposition-deterrent chemicals in female cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). *J. Insect Phys.* 47, 951–956.
- Haile, F., Nowatzki, T., and Storer, N. (2021). Overview of pest status, potential risk, and management considerations of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) for U.S. Soybean production. *J. Integrated Pest Manage.* 12, 1. doi: 10.1093/jipm/pmaa030
- Hansen, E. M., Reeser, P. W., and Sutton, W. (2012). *Phytophthora* beyond agriculture. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 50, 359–378. doi: 10.1146/annurev-phyto-081211-172946
- Hantula, J., Lilja, A., Nuorteva, H., Parikka, P., and Werres, S. (2000). Pathogenicity, morphology and genetic variation of *Phytophthora cactorum* from strawberry, apple, rhododendron, and silver birch. *Mycol. Res.* 104, 1062–1068. doi: 10.1017/S0953756200002999
- Hardham, A. R., and Blackman, L. M. (2018). *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *Mol. Plant Pathol.* 19, 260–285. doi: 10.1111/mpp.2018.19.issue-2
- Hardy, G., Barrett, S., and Shearer, B. L. (2001). The future of phosphite as a fungicide to control the soilborne plant pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in natural ecosystems. *Australas. Plant Pathol.* 30, 133–139. doi: 10.1071/AP01012
- Harris, D. C. (1991). The *Phytophthora* diseases of apple. *J. Hort. Sci.* 66, 513–544. doi: 10.1080/00221589.1991.11516181
- Harris, A. R., and Webber, J. (2016). Sporulation potential, symptom expression and detection of *Phytophthora ramorum* on larch needles and other foliar hosts. *Plant Pathol.* 65, 1441–1451. doi: 10.1111/ppa.2016.65.issue-9
- Haye, T., Abdallah, S., Garipey, T., and Wyniger, D. (2014). Phenology, life table analysis and temperature requirements of the invasive brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, in Europe. *J. Pest Sci.* 87, 407–418. doi: 10.1007/s10340-014-0560-z
- Heil, M. (2014). Herbivore-induced plant volatiles: targets, perception and unanswered questions. *New Phytol.* 204, 297–306. doi: 10.1111/nph.2014.204.issue-2
- Henderson, D., Williams, C. J., and Miller, J. S. (2007). Forecasting late blight in potato crops of Southern Idaho using logistic regression analysis. *Plant Dis.* 91, 951–956. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-91-8-0951
- Hirata, A., Nakamura, K., Nakao, K., Kominami, Y., Tanaka, N., and Ohashi, H. (2017). Potential distribution of pine wilt disease under future climate change scenarios. *PLoS One* 12, e0182837. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182837
- Ho, S. S. H., Wang, L., Chow, J. C., Watson, J. G., Xue, Y., Huang, Y., et al. (2018). Optimization and evaluation of multi-bed adsorbent tube method in collection of volatile organic compounds. *Atmospheric Res.* 202, 187–195. doi: 10.1016/j.atmosres.2017.11.026
- Hoballah, M. E. F., Tamò, C., and Turlings, T. C. (2002). Differential attractiveness of induced odors emitted by eight maize varieties for the parasitoid *Cotesia marginiventris*: is quality or quantity important? *J. Chem. Ecol.* 28, 951–968. doi: 10.1023/A:1015253600083
- Hruska, A. J., and Gould, F. (1997). Fall armyworm (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and *Diatraea lineolata* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae): impact of larval population level and temporal occurrence on maize yield in Nicaragua. *J. Economic Entomology* 90, 611–622. doi: 10.1093/jeep/90.2.611
- Huai, W. X., Tian, G., Hansen, E. M., Zhao, W.-X., Goheen, E. M., Grünwald, N. J., et al. (2013). Identification of *Phytophthora* species baited and isolated from forest soil and streams in northwestern Yunnan province, China. *For. Pathol.* 43, 87–103. doi: 10.1111/efp.2013.43.issue-2
- Huang, X.-Z., Chen, J.-Y., Xiao, H.-J., Xiao, Y.-T., Wu, J., Wu, J.-X., et al. (2015). Dynamic transcriptome analysis and volatile profiling of *Gossypium hirsutum* in response to the cotton bollworm *Helicoverpa armigera*. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 11867. doi: 10.1038/srep11867
- Hwang, H. S., Han, J. Y., and Choi, Y. E. (2021). Enhanced emission of Monoterpene 3-Carene in *Pinus densiflora* infected by pine wood nematode and characterization of 3-Carene Synthase. *Forests* 12, 514. doi: 10.3390/f12050514
- Inácio, M. L., Nóbrega, F., Vieira, P., Bonifácio, L., Naves, P., Sousa, E., et al. (2015). First detection of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* associated with *Pinus nigra* in Portugal and in Europe. *For. Pathol.* 45, 235–238. doi: 10.1111/efp.2015.45.issue-3
- Jeleń, H. H., Krawczyk, J., Larsen, T. O., Jarosz, A., and Gołębniak, B. (2005). Main compounds responsible for off-odour of strawberries infected by *Phytophthora cactorum*. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.* 40, 255–259. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-765X.2005.01668.x
- Jiang, N. J., Mo, B. T., Guo, H., Yang, J., Tang, R., and Wang, C. Z. (2022). Revisiting the sex pheromone of the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*, a new invasive pest in South China. *Insect Sci.* 29, 865–878. doi: 10.1111/1744-7917.12956
- Jin, L., Zhang, H., Lu, Y., Yang, Y., Wu, K., Tabashnik, B. E., et al. (2015). Large-scale test of natural refuge strategy for delaying insect resistance to transgenic bt crops. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 33, 169–174. doi: 10.1038/nbt.3100
- Johnson, S. J. (1987). Migration and the life history strategy of the fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* in the Western Hemisphere. *Insect Sci. Appl.* 8, 543–549. doi: 10.1017/S1742758400022591
- Jones, J. T., Moens, M., Mota, M., Li, H., and Kikuchi, T. (2008). *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*: opportunities in comparative genomics and molecular host-parasite interactions. *Mol. Plant Pathol.* 9, 357–368. doi: 10.1111/j.1364-3703.2007.00461.x
- Jones, C. M., Papanicolaou, A., Mironidis, G. K., Voontas, J., Yang, Y., Lim, K., et al. (2015). Genome-wide transcriptional signatures of migratory flight activity in a globally invasive insect pest. *Mol. Ecol.* 24, 4901–4911. doi: 10.1111/mec.2015.24.issue-19
- Jones, M. J., Parry, H., Tay, W. T., Reynolds, D. R., and Chapman, J. W. (2019). Movement ecology of pest *Helicoverpa*: Implications for ongoing spread. *Annu. Rev. Entomology* 64, 279–295. doi: 10.1146/annurev-ento-011118-111959
- Jung, T. (2009). Beech decline in Central Europe driven by the interaction between *Phytophthora* infections and climatic extremes. *For. Pathol.* 39, 73–94. doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0329.2008.00566.x
- Jung, T., Blaschke, H., and Oßwald, W. (2000). Involvement of soilborne *Phytophthora* species in Central European oak decline and the effect of site factors on the disease. *Plant Pathol.* 49, 706–718. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-3059.2000.00521.x
- Jung, T., and Burgess, T. I. (2009). Re-evaluation of *Phytophthora citricola* isolates from multiple woody hosts in Europe and North America reveals a new species. *Phytophthora plurivora* nov. *Persoonia* sp 22, 95–110. doi: 10.3767/003158509X442612
- Jung, T., Chang, T.-T., Bakonyi, J., Seress, D., Pérez-Sierra, A., Yang, X., et al. (2017a). Diversity of *Phytophthora* species in natural ecosystems of Taiwan and association with disease symptoms. *Plant Pathol.* 66, 194–211. doi: 10.1111/ppa.2017.66.issue-2
- Jung, T., Durán, A., von Stowasser, E. S., Schena, L., Mosca, S., Fajardo, S., et al. (2018b). Diversity of *Phytophthora* species in Valdivian rainforests and association with severe dieback symptoms. *For. Pathol.* 48, e12443. doi: 10.1111/efp.2018.48.issue-5
- Jung, T., Horta Jung, M., Scanu, B., Seress, D., Kovács, D. M., Maia, C., et al. (2017b). Six new *Phytophthora* species from ITS Clade 7a including two sexually functional heterothallic hybrid species detected in natural ecosystems in Taiwan. *Persoonia* 38, 100–135. doi: 10.3767/003158517X693615

- Jung, T., Horta Jung, M., Webber, J. F., Kageyama, K., Hieno, A., Masuya, H., et al. (2021). The destructive tree pathogen *Phytophthora ramorum* originates from the Laurosilva forests of East Asia. *J. Fungi* 7, 226. doi: 10.3390/jof7030226
- Jung, T., La Spada, F., Pane, A., Aloï, F., Evoli, M., Horta Jung, M., et al. (2019). Diversity and distribution of *Phytophthora* species in protected natural areas in Sicily. *Forests* 10, 259. doi: 10.3390/f10030259
- Jung, T., Milenković, I., Balci, Y., Janoušek, J., Kudláček, T., Nagy, Z.Á., et al. (2024). Worldwide forest surveys reveal forty-three new species in *Phytophthora* major Clade 2 with fundamental implications for the evolution and biogeography of the genus and global plant biosecurity. *Stud. Mycology* 107, 251–388. doi: 10.3114/sim.2024.107.04
- Jung, T., Milenković, I., Corcobado, T., Májek, T., Janoušek, J., Kudláček, T., et al. (2022). Extensive morphological and behavioural diversity among fourteen new and seven described species in *Phytophthora* Clade 10 and its evolutionary implications. *Persoonia* 49, 1–57. doi: 10.3767/persoonia.2022.49.01
- Jung, T., Orlikowski, L., Henricot, B., Abad-Campos, P., Aday, A. G., Aguín Casal, O., et al. (2016). Widespread *Phytophthora* infestations in European nurseries put forest, semi-natural and horticultural ecosystems at high risk of *Phytophthora* diseases. *For. Pathol.* 46, 134–163. doi: 10.1111/efp.2016.46.issue-2
- Jung, T., Pérez-Sierra, A., Durán, A., Horta Jung, M., Balci, Y., and Scanu, B. (2018a). Canker and decline diseases caused by soil- and airborne *Phytophthora* species in forests and woodlands. *Persoonia* 40, 182–220. doi: 10.3767/persoonia.2018.40.08
- Jung, T., Scanu, B., Brasier, C. M., Webber, J., Milenković, I., Corcobado, T., et al. (2020). A survey in natural forest ecosystems of Vietnam reveals high diversity of both new and described *Phytophthora* taxa including *P. ramorum*. *Forests* 11, 93. doi: 10.3390/f11010093
- Kamata, N. (2008). "Integrated pest management of pine wilt disease in Japan: Tactics and strategies," in *Pine wilt disease* (Springer Japan, Tokyo), 304–322.
- Karban, R., Yang, L. H., and Edwards, K. F. (2014). Volatile communication between plants that affects herbivory: a meta-analysis. *Ecol. Lett.* 17, 44–52. doi: 10.1111/ele.2013.17.issue-1
- Karimi, A., and Gross, J. (2024). Development and validation of an innovative headspace collection technique: volatile organic compound patterns emitted by different developmental stages of *Halyomorpha halys*. *Front. Horticulture* 3, 1380008. doi: 10.3389/fhort.2024.1380008
- Kenis, M., Benelli, G., Biondi, A., Calatayud, P. A., Day, R., Desneux, N., et al. (2022). Invasiveness, biology, ecology, and management of the fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *Entomologia Generalis* 43, 187–1241. doi: 10.1127/entomologia/2022/1659
- Khrimian, A., Zhang, A., Weber, D. C., Ho, H.-Y., Aldrich, J. R., Vermillion, K. E., et al. (2014). Discovery of the aggregation pheromone of the brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha halys*) through the creation of stereoisomeric libraries of 1-bisabolen-3-ols. *J. Natural Products* 77, 1708–1717. doi: 10.1021/np5003753
- Kim, J., Lee, S. M., and Park, C. G. (2016). *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* is killed by homologues of 2-(1-undecyloxy)-1-ethanol. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 1–5. doi: 10.1038/srep29300
- Kitamura, C., Wakamura, S., and Takahashi, S. (1984). Identification and functions of ventral glands secretion of some Heteroptera. *Appl. Entomology Zoology* 19, 33–41. doi: 10.1303/aez.19.33
- Kment, P., and Vilimova, J. (2010). Thoracic scent efferent system of Pentatomoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera): a review of terminology. *Zootaxa* 2706, 1–77. doi: 10.11646/zootaxa.2706.1.1
- Kuroda, K. (2008). "Physiological incidences related to symptom development and wilting mechanism," in *Pine wilt disease* (Springer, Japan, Tokyo), 204–222.
- Lamsal, S., Sibi, S., and Yadav, S. (2020). Fall armyworm in South Asia: Threats and management. *Asian J. Adv. Agric. Res.* 13, 21–34. doi: 10.9734/ajaaar/2020/v13i330106
- Laothawornkitkul, J., Jansen, R. M. C., Smid, H. M., Bouwmeester, H. J., Muller, J., and Van Bruggen, A. H. C. (2010). Volatile organic compounds as a diagnostic marker of late blight infected potato plants: A pilot study. *Crop Prot.* 29, 872–878. doi: 10.1016/j.cpro.2010.03.003
- Lee, D. H., Short, B. D., Joseph, S. V., Bergh, J. C., and Leskey, T. C. (2013). Review of the biology, ecology, and management of *Halyomorpha halys* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in China, Japan, and the Republic of Korea. *Environ. Entomology* 42, 627–641. doi: 10.1603/EN13006
- Leskey, T. C., and Nielsen, A. L. (2018). Impact of the invasive brown marmorated stink bug in north america and europe: history, biology, ecology, and Management. *Annu. Rev. Entomology* 63, 599–618. doi: 10.1146/annurev-ento-020117-043226
- Leskey, T. C., Short, B. D., Butler, B. R., and Wright, S. E. (2012). Impact of the invasive brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål), in mid-Atlantic tree fruit orchards in the United States: case studies of commercial management. *Psyche* 2012, 535062. doi: 10.1155/2012/535062
- Li, Z., Paul, R., Ba Tis, T., Saville, A. C., Hansel, J. C., Yu, T., et al. (2019). Non-invasive plant disease diagnostics enabled by smartphone-based fingerprinting of leaf volatiles. *Nat. Plants* 5, 856–866. doi: 10.1038/s41477-019-0476-y
- Lima, E. R., and McNeil, J. N. (2009). Female sex pheromones in the host races and hybrids of the fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Chemoecology* 19, 29–36. doi: 10.1007/s00049-009-0005-y
- Liu, T., Wang, J., Hu, X., and Feng, J. (2020). Land-use change drives present and future distributions of Fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Sci. Total Environ.* 706, 135872. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135872
- Liu, M., Yu, H., and Li, G. (2008). Oviposition deterrents from eggs of the cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae): chemical identification and analysis by electroantennogram. *J. Insect Phys.* 54, 656–662. doi: 10.1016/j.jinsphys.2008.01.002
- Lockwood, J. A., and Story, R. N. (1985). Bifunctional pheromone in the first instar of the southern green stink bug, *nezara viridula* (L.) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae): its characterization and interaction with other stimuli. *Ann. Entomological Soc. America* 78 (4), 474–479.
- Lockwood, J. A., and Story, R. N. (1987). Defensive secretion of the southern green stink bug (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) as an alarm pheromone. *Ann. Entomological Soc. America* 80 (5), 686–691.
- Loreto, F., and Schnitzler, J. P. (2010). Abiotic stresses and induced BVOCs. *Trends Plant Sci.* 15, 154–166. doi: 10.1016/j.tplants.2009.12.006
- Loulier, J., Lefort, F., Stocki, M., Asztemborska, M., Szmigielski, R., Siwek, K., et al. (2020). Detection of fungi and oomycetes by volatiles using E-Nose and SPME-GC/MS platforms. *Molecules* 25, 5749. doi: 10.3390/molecules25235749
- Lu, X., Sun, D., Rookes, J. E., Kong, L., Zhang, X., and Cahill, D. M. (2019). Nanoapplication of a resistance inducer to reduce *Phytophthora* disease in pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L.). *Front. Plant Sci.* 10, 1238. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.01238
- MacDougall, S., Bayansal, F., and Ahmadi, A. (2022). Emerging methods of monitoring volatile organic compounds for detection of plant pests and disease. *Biosensors* 12, 239. doi: 10.3390/bios12040239
- Mamiya, Y. (1983). Pathology of the pine wilt disease caused by *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 21, 201–220. doi: 10.1146/annurev.py.21.090183.001221
- Martínez, M. T., Cuenca, B., Mosteiro, F., Piñeiro, P., Pérez, F., Solla, A., et al. (2023). Screening of cork oak for resistance to *Phytophthora cinnamomi* and micropropagation of tolerant seedlings. *Horticulturae* 9, 692. doi: 10.3390/horticulturae9060692
- McCartney, M. M., Roubtsova, T. V., Yamaguchi, M. S., Kasuga, T., Ebeler, S. E., Davis, C. E., et al. (2018). Effects of *Phytophthora ramorum* on volatile organic compound emissions of *Rhododendron* using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. *Analytical Bioanalytical Chem.* 410, 1475–1487. doi: 10.1007/s00216-017-0789-5
- McConnell, M., and Balci, Y. (2014). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a contributor to white oak decline in mid-Atlantic United States forests. *Plant Dis.* 98, 319–327. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-06-13-0649-RE
- Meentemeyer, R. K., Rizzo, D., Mark, W., and Lotz, E. (2004). Mapping the risk of establishment and spread of sudden oak death in California. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 200, 195–214. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2004.06.021
- Menéndez-Gutiérrez, M., Alonso, M., Toval, G., and Díaz, R. (2018). Testing of selected *Pinus pinaster* half-sib families for tolerance to pinewood nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*). *Forestry* 91, 38–48. doi: 10.1093/forestry/cpx030
- Mircetich, S. M., and Matheron, M. E. (1976). *Phytophthora* root and crown rot of cherry trees. *Phytopathology* 66, 549–558. doi: 10.1094/Phyto-66-549
- Moore, L. C., Tirello, P., Scaccini, D., Toews, M. D., Duso, C., and Pozzebon, A. (2019). Characterizing damage potential of the brown marmorated stink bug (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in cherry orchards. *Entomologia Generalis* 39, 271–283. doi: 10.1127/entomologia/2019/0799
- Mota, M. M., Braasch, H., Bravo, M. A., Penas, A. C., Burgermeister, W., Metge, K., et al. (1999). First report of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* in Portugal and in Europe. *Nematology* 1, 727–734. doi: 10.1163/156854199508757
- Mullett, M. S., Van Poucke, K., Haegeman, A., Focquet, F., Cauldron, N. C., Knaus, B. J., et al. (2023). Phylogeography and population structure of the global, wide host-range hybrid pathogen *Phytophthora × cambivora*. *IMA Fungus* 14, 4. doi: 10.1186/s43008-023-00109-6
- Nakamura, K. (2008). "Attraction trap for monitoring *Monochamus alternatus* adults - its usefulness and limitations," in *Pine wilt disease: A worldwide threat to forest ecosystems* (Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht), 369–378.
- Nesbitt, B., Beevor, P., Hall, D., and Lester, R. (1980). (Z)-9-Hexadecenal: a minor component of the female sex pheromone of *Heliothis armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae). *Entomologia Experimentalis Applicata* 27, 306–308. doi: 10.1111/j.1570-7458.1980.tb02979.x
- Nixon, L. J., Ludwick, D. C., and Leskey, T. C. (2021). Horizontal and vertical dispersal capacity and effects of fluorescent marking on *Lycorma delicatula* nymphs and adults. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata* 169 (2), 219–226. doi: 10.1093/jeec/toad038
- Nixon, L. J., Morrison, W. R., Rice, K. B., Brockerhoff, E. G., Leskey, T. C., Guzman, F., et al. (2018). Identification of volatiles released by diapausing brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae). *PLoS One* 13, e0191223. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0191223
- Nixon, L. J., Tabb, A., Morrison, W. R., Rice, K. B., Brockerhoff, E. G., Leskey, T. C., et al. (2019). Volatile release, mobility, and mortality of diapausing *Halyomorpha halys* during simulated shipping movements and temperature changes. *J. Pest Sci.* 92, 633–641.
- Noge, K., Prudic, K. L., and Becerra, J. X. (2012). Defensive roles of (E)-2-Alkenals and related compounds in heteroptera. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 38, 1050–1056. doi: 10.1007/s10886-012-0166-y

- Nordström, I., Sherwood, P., Bohman, B., Woodward, S., Peterson, D. L., Niño-Sánchez, J., et al. (2022). Utilizing volatile organic compounds for early detection of *Fusarium circinatum*. *Sci. Rep.* 12, 21661. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-26078-1
- Nose, M., and Shiraishi, S. (2008). "Breeding for resistance to pine wilt disease," in *Pine wilt disease*. Eds. Z. B.G., K. Futai, J. R. Sutherland and Y. Takeuchi (Springer, Tokyo), 334–350.
- O'Hanlon, R., Choiseul, J., Brennan, J. M., and Grogan, H. (2018). Assessment of the eradication treatments applied to *Phytophthora ramorum* in Irish *Larix kaempferi* forests. *For. Pathol.* 48, e12389. doi: 10.1111/efp.12389
- O'Hanlon, R., Choiseul, J., Corrigan, M., Catarame, T., and Destefanis, M. (2016). Diversity and detections of *Phytophthora* species from trade and non-trade environments in Ireland. *EPP0 Bull.* 46, 594–602. doi: 10.1111/efp.12331
- Orlikowski, L. B., Ptaszek, M., Rodziewicz, A., Nechwatal, J., Thinggaard, K., and Jung, T. (2011). *Phytophthora* root and collar rot of mature *Fraxinus excelsior* in forest stands in Poland and Denmark. *For. Pathol.* 41, 510–519. doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0329.2011.00714.x
- Paré, P. W., and Tumlinson, J. H. (1999). Plant volatiles as a defense against insect herbivores. *Plant Physiol.* 121, 325–331. doi: 10.1104/pp.121.2.325
- Peñaflor, M. F. G. V., Erb, M., Robert, C. A. M., et al. (2011). Oviposition by a moth suppresses constitutive and herbivore-induced plant volatiles in maize. *Planta* 234, 207–215. doi: 10.1007/s00425-011-1409-9
- Pérez-Sierra, A., and Jung, T. (2013). "Phytophthora in woody ornamental nurseries," in *Phytophthora: A global perspective*. Ed. K. Lamour (CABI, Wallingford, UK), 166–177.
- Peterson, E. K., Hansen, E. M., and Kanaskie, A. (2015). Temporal epidemiology of sudden oak death in Oregon. *Phytopathology* 105, 937–946. doi: 10.1094/PHYTO-12-14-0348-FI
- Peterson, H. M., Ray, S., Ali, J. G., and Krawczyk, G. (2022). Feeding and oviposition by the brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål) induce direct and systemic changes in volatile compound emissions from potted peach and tree of heaven. *Arthropod-Plant Interact.* 16, 227–247. doi: 10.1007/s11829-022-09893-1
- Piccardi, P., Capizzi, A., Cassani, G., Spinelli, P., Arsura, E., and Massardo, P. (1977). A sex pheromone component of the old world bollworm *Heliothis armigera*. *J. Insect Physiol.* 23, 1443–1445. doi: 10.1016/0022-1910(77)90170-6
- Pinto-Zevallos, D. M., Strapasson, P., and Zarbin, P. H. G. (2016). Herbivore-induced volatile organic compounds emitted by maize: Electrophysiological responses in *Spodoptera frugiperda* females. *Phytochem. Lett.* 16, 70–74. doi: 10.1016/j.phytol.2016.03.005
- Pitre, H. N., and Hogg, D. B. (1983). Development of the fall armyworm on cotton, soybean and corn. *J. Georgia Entomological Soc.* 18, 187–194.
- Qiu, R., Qu, D., Hardy, G. E. S. J., Trengove, R., Agarwal, M., and Ren, Y. (2014a). Optimization of headspace solid-phase microextraction conditions for the identification of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* rands. *Plant Dis.* 98, 1088–1098. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-12-13-1258-RE
- Qiu, R., Qu, D., Trengove, R., Agarwal, M., Hardy, G. E. S. J., and Ren, Y. (2014b). Headspace solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry for analysis of VOCs produced by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *Plant Dis.* 98, 1099–1105. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-01-14-0049-RE
- Reeser, P. W., Sutton, W., Hansen, E. M., Remigi, P., and Adams, G. C. (2011). *Phytophthora* species in forest streams in Oregon and Alaska. *Mycologia* 103, 22–35. doi: 10.3852/10-013
- Riaz, S., Johnson, J. B., Ahmad, M., Fitt, G. P., and Naiker, M. (2021). A review in biological interactions and management of the cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *J. Appl. Entomology* 145, 467–498. doi: 10.1111/jen.v145.6
- Rice, K. B., Bergh, C. J., Bergmann, E. J., Biddinger, D. J., Dieckhoff, C., Dively, G., et al. (2014). Biology, ecology, and management of brown marmorated stink bug (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae). *J. Integrated Pest Manage.* 5, 1–13. doi: 10.1603/IPM14002
- Rizzo, D. M., Garbelotto, M., Davidson, J. M., Slaughter, G. W., and Koike, S. T. (2002). *Phytophthora ramorum* as the cause of extensive mortality of *Quercus* spp. and *Lithocarpus densiflorus* in California. *Plant Dis.* 86, 205–214. doi: 10.1094/PDIS.2002.86.3.205
- Rizzo, D. M., Garbelotto, M., and Hansen, E. M. (2005). *Phytophthora ramorum*: integrative research and management of an emerging pathogen in California and Oregon forests. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 43, 309–335. doi: 10.1146/annurev.phyto.42.040803.140418
- Robert, C. A., Erb, M., Hiltbold, I., Hibbard, B. E., Gaillard, M. D., Bilal, J., et al. (2013). Genetically engineered maize plants reveal distinct costs and benefits of constitutive volatile emissions in the field. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* 11 (5), 628–639. doi: 10.1111/pbi.12053
- Robin, C., Morel, O., Vettraino, A. M., Perlerou, C., Diamandis, S., and Vannini, A. (2006). Genetic variation in susceptibility to *Phytophthora cambivora* in European chestnut (*Castanea sativa*). *For. Ecol. Manage.* 226, 199–207. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2006.01.035
- Rodrigues, J. M. (2008). "National eradication programme for the pinewood nematode," in *Pine wilt disease: A worldwide threat to forest ecosystems*. Eds. M. M. Mota and P. Vieira (Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht), 5–14.
- Rwomushana, I., Bateman, M., Beale, T., Beseh, P., Cameron, K., Chiluba, M., et al. (2018). Fall armyworm: impacts and implications for Africa October 2018. *Evidence note Update Outbreaks Pest Manage.* 28, 18–19. doi: 10.1564/v28_oct_02
- Sabbatini Peverieri, G., Talamas, E., Bon, M. C., Marianelli, L., Bernardinelli, I., Malossini, G., et al. (2018). Two Asian egg parasitoids of *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål) (Hemiptera, Pentatomidae) emerge in northern Italy: *Trissolcus mitsukurii* (Ashmead) and *Trissolcus japonicus* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae). *J. Hymenoptera Res.* 67, 37–53. doi: 10.3897/jhr.67.30883
- Sanfuentes, E., González, M., Castillo, M., Rubilar, R., Besoain, X., Sanhueza, C., et al. (2022). Detection of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on declining *Araucaria araucana* forests. *For. Pathol.* 52, e12765. doi: 10.1111/efp.12765
- Santos, C., Nelson, C. D., Zhebentyayeva, T., MaChado, H., Gomes-Laranjo, J., and Costa, R. L. (2017). First interspecific genetic linkage map for *Castanea sativa* x *Castanea crenata* revealed QTLs for resistance to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *PLoS One* 12, e0184381. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0184381
- Santos, M. D., L., Resend, M. L. V., Alves, G. S. C., Huguet-Tapia, J. C., Resende, M. F. R. Jr., and Brawner, J. T. (2022). Genome-Wide Identification, characterization, and comparative analysis of NLR resistance genes in *Coffea*. *Front. Plant Sci.* spp 13, 868581. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2022.868581
- Scaccini, D., Falagiarda, M., Tortorici, F., Martinez-Sañudo, I., Tirello, P., Reyes-Dominguez, Y., et al. (2020). An insight into the role of *Trissolcus mitsukurii* as biological control agent of *Halyomorpha halys* in Northeastern Italy. *Insects* 11, 1–16. doi: 10.3390/insects11050306
- Schuman, M. C. (2023). Where, when, and why do plant volatiles mediate ecological signaling? The answer is blowing in the wind. *Annual Review of Plant Biol.* 74, 609–633. doi: 10.1146/annurev-arplant-040121-114908
- Sekul, A. A., and Sparks, A. N. (1967). Sex pheromone of the fall armyworm moth: Isolation, identification, and synthesis. *J. Economic Entomology* 60, 1270–1272. doi: 10.1093/jee/60.5.1270
- Shakya, S. K., Grünwald, N. J., Fieland, V. J., Knaus, B. J., Weiland, J. E., Maia, C., et al. (2021). Phylogeography of the wide-host range panglobal plant pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *Mol. Ecol.* 30, 5164–5178. doi: 10.1111/mec.v30.20
- Sharanabasappa, D., Kalleshwara Swamy, C. M., Asokan, R., Swamy, H. M. M., Maruthi, M. S., Pavithra, H. B., et al. (2018). First report of the Fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (JE Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), an alien invasive pest on maize in India. *Pest Manage. Hortic. Ecosyst.* 24, 23–29.
- Shearer, B. L., Crane, C. E., and Cochrane, A. (2004). Quantification of the susceptibility of the native flora of the South-West Botanical Province, Western Australia, to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *Aust. J. Bot.* 52, 435–443. doi: 10.1071/BT03131
- Shearer, B. L., and Tippett, J. T. (1989). *Jarrah Dieback: The dynamics and management of Phytophthora cinnamomi in the Jarrah Eucalyptus marginata forest of South-Western Australia* Vol. 3 (Como, Western Australia: Department of Conservation and Land Management, Research Bulletin), 76.
- Sherwood, P., Nordström, I., Woodward, S., Bohman, B., and Cleary, M. (2024). Detecting pathogenic *Phytophthora* species using volatile organic compounds. *Molecules* 29, 1749. doi: 10.3390/molecules29081749
- Shimazu, M. (2008). "Biological control of the Japanese pine sawyer beetle, *monochamus alternatus*," in *Pine wilt disease*. Eds. B. G. Zhao, K. Futai, J. R. Sutherland and Y. Takeuchi (Springer, Tokyo), 351–370.
- Shivaramu, S., Jayanthi, P. D. K., Kempraj, V., Anjinappa, R., Nandagopal, B., and Chakravarty, A. K. (2017). What signals do herbivore-induced plant volatiles provide conspecific herbivores? *Arthropod-Plant Interact.* 11, 815–823. doi: 10.1007/s11829-017-9536-2
- Snieszko, R. A., Johnson, J. S., Reeser, P., Kegley, A., Hansen, E. M., Sutton, W., et al. (2019). Genetic resistance to *Phytophthora lateralis* in Port-Orford cedar (*Chamaecyparis lawsoniana*) – Basic building blocks for a resistance program. *Plants People Planet* 2, 69–83. doi: 10.1002/ppp3.10081
- Solla, A., Moreno, G., Malewski, T., Jung, T., Klisz, M., Tkaczyk, M., et al. (2021). Phosphite spray for the control of oak decline induced by *Phytophthora* in Europe. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 485, 118938. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2021.118938
- Solomon, D., Dutcher, D., and Raymond, T. (2013). Characterization of *Halyomorpha halys* (brown marmorated stink bug) biogenic volatile organic compound emissions and their role in secondary organic aerosol formation. *J. Air Waste Manage. Assoc.* 63, 1264–1269. doi: 10.1080/10962247.2013.819047
- Sparks, A. N. (1979). A review of the biology of the fall armyworm. *Florida Entomologist* 62, 82–87. doi: 10.2307/3494083
- Stahl, J., Tortorici, F., Pontini, M., Bon, M. C., Hoelmer, K., Marazzi, C., et al. (2019). First discovery of adventive populations of *Trissolcus japonicus* in Europe. *J. Pest Sci.* 92, 371–379. doi: 10.1007/s10340-018-1061-2
- Stukely, M. J. C., Crane, C. E., McComb, J. A., and Bennett, I. J. (2007). Field survival and growth of clonal, micropropagated *Eucalyptus marginata* selected for resistance to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 238, 330–334. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2006.10.028
- Sturaro, A., Parvoli, G., and Doretto, L. (1994). A simple and fast sampling method for the characterization of volatile compounds released by nezara viridula. *Chromatographia* 39 (1), 103–106.

- Sutherland, J. R. (2008). "A brief overview of the pine wood nematode and pine wilt disease in Canada and the United States." in *Pine wilt disease*. Eds. B. G. Zhao, K. Futai, J. R. Sutherland and Y. Takeuchi (Springer, Tokyo), 13–17.
- Tabashnik, B. E., and Carrière, Y. (2017). Surge in insect resistance to transgenic crops and prospects for sustainability. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 31, 926–935. doi: 10.1038/nbt.3974
- Takeuchi, Y., Kanzaki, N., and Futai, K. (2006). Volatile compounds in pine stands suffering from pine wilt disease: qualitative and quantitative evaluation. *Nematology* 8, 869–879. doi: 10.1163/1568541067799295
- Talamas, E. J., Herlihy, M. V., Dieckhoff, C., Hoelmer, K. A., Buffington, M., Bon, M. C., et al. (2019). Trapping for early detection of the brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, in New Zealand. *New Z. Plant Prot.* 72, 36–43. doi: 10.30843/nzpp.2019.72.316
- Tambo, J. A., Day, R. K., Lamontagne-Godwin, J., Silvestri, S., Beseh, P. K., Oppong-Mensah, B., et al. (2020). Tackling fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) outbreak in Africa: an analysis of farmers' control actions. *Int. J. Pest Manage.* 66, 298–310. doi: 10.1080/09670874.2019.1646942
- Tay, W. T., Meagher, R. L. Jr., Czapak, C., and Groot, A. T. (2023). *Spodoptera frugiperda*: ecology, evolution, and management options of an invasive species. *Annu. Rev. Entomology* 68, 299–317. doi: 10.1146/annurev-ento-120220-102548
- Tay, W. T., Soria, M. F., Walsh, T., Thomazoni, D., Silvie, P., Behere, G. T., et al. (2013). A brave new world for an old world pest *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in Brazil. *PLoS One* 8, e80134. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080134
- Tholl, D., Hossain, O., Weinhold, A., Röse, U. S., and Wei, Q. (2021). Trends and applications in plant volatile sampling and analysis. *Plant J.* 106, 314–325. doi: 10.1111/tpj.v106.2
- Todd, E. L., and Poole, R. W. (1980). Keys and illustrations for the armyworm moths of the noctuid genus *Spodoptera* Guenée from the Western Hemisphere. *Ann. Entomological Soc. America* 73, 722–738. doi: 10.1093/acesa/73.6.722
- Tognon, R., Aldrich, J. R., Buffington, M. L., Talamas, E. J., Sant'Ana, J., and Zalom, F. G. (2017). *Halyomorpha halys* (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) egg surface chemicals inhibit North American *Telenomus* and *Trissolcus* (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae) parasitism. *Biol. Control* 114, 39–44. doi: 10.1016/j.biocontrol.2017.07.014
- Tumlinson, J. H., Mitchell, E. R., Teal, P. E. A., Heath, R. R., and Mengelkoch, L. J. (1986). Sex pheromone of fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J. E. Smith), identification of components critical to attraction in the field. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 12, 1909–1926. doi: 10.1007/BF01041855
- Tumlinson, J. H., Mitchell, E. R., and Yu, H. S. (1990). Analysis and field evaluation of volatile blend emitted by calling virgin females of beet armyworm moth, *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner). *J. Chem. Ecol.* 16, 3411–3423. doi: 10.1007/BF00982107
- Turlings, T. C. J., Alborn, H. T., Loughrin, J. H., and Tumlinson, J. H. (2000). Volicitin, an elicitor of maize volatiles in the oral secretion of *Spodoptera exigua*: its isolation and bio-activity. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 26, 189–202. doi: 10.1023/A:1005449730052
- Turlings, T. C., Bernasconi, M., Bertossa, R., Bigler, F., Caloz, G., and Dorn, S. (1998a). The induction of volatile emissions in maize by three herbivore species with different feeding habits: possible consequences for their natural enemies. *Biol. Control* 11 (2), 122–129. doi: 10.1006/bcon.1997.0591
- Turlings, T. C., and Degen, T. (2022). The role of herbivore-induced plant volatiles in trophic interactions: The Swiss Connection. *Chimia* 76, 900–900. doi: 10.2533/chimia.2022.900
- Turlings, T. C., and Erb, M. (2018). Tritrophic interactions mediated by herbivore-induced plant volatiles: mechanisms, ecological relevance, and application potential. *Annu. Rev. Entomology* 63, 433–452. doi: 10.1146/annurev-ento-020117-043507
- Turlings, T., Lengwiler, U., Bernasconi, M., et al. (1998b). Timing of induced volatile emissions in maize seedlings. *Planta* 207, 146–152. doi: 10.1007/s004250050466
- Turlings, T. C. J., McCall, P. J., Alborn, H. T., and Tumlinson, J. H. (1993). An elicitor in caterpillar oral secretions that induces corn seedlings to emit chemical signals attractive to parasitic wasps. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 19, 411–425. doi: 10.1007/BF00994314
- Turlings, T. C., and Tumlinson, J. H. (1992). Systemic release of chemical signals by herbivore-injured corn. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 89, 8399–8402. doi: 10.1073/pnas.89.17.8399
- Vandervoet, T. F., Bellamy, D. E., Anderson, D., and MacLellan, R. (2019). Trapping for early detection of the brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, in New Zealand. *New Z. Plant Prot.* 72, 36–43. doi: 10.30843/nzpp.2019.72.316
- Van Poucke, K., Franceschini, S., Webber, J. F., Vercauteren, A., Turner, J. A., McCracken, A. R., et al. (2012). Discovery of a fourth evolutionary lineage of *Phytophthora ramorum*: EU2. *Fungal Biol.* 116, 1178–1191. doi: 10.1016/j.funbio.2012.09.003
- Vettraino, A. M., Brasier, C. M., Brown, A. V., and Vannini, A. (2011). *Phytophthora himalsilva* sp. nov. an unusually phenotypically variable species from a remote forest in Nepal. *Fungal Biol.* 115, 275–287. doi: 10.1016/j.funbio.2010.12.013
- Vettraino, A. M., Morel, O., Perlerou, C., Robin, C., Diamandis, S., and Vannini, A. (2005). Occurrence and distribution of *Phytophthora* species associated with Ink Disease of chestnut in Europe. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 111, 169–180. doi: 10.1007/s10658-004-1882-0
- Vicente, C., Espada, M., Vieira, P., and Mota, M. (2012). Pine wilt disease: a threat to European forestry. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 133, 89–99. doi: 10.1007/s10658-011-9924-x
- Vieira, N. F., Pomari-Fernandes, A., Lemes, A. A., Vacari, A. M., De Bortoli, S. A., and de Freitas Bueno, A. (2017). Cost of production of *Telenomus remus* (Hymenoptera: Platygasteridae) grown in natural and alternative hosts. *J. Economic Entomology* 110, 2724–2726. doi: 10.1093/jee/tox271
- Von Broembsen, S. L., and Kruger, F. J. (1985). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* associated with mortality of native vegetation in South Africa. *Plant Dis.* 69, 715–717. doi: 10.1094/PD-69-715
- Wakamura, S., Arakaki, N., and Yoshimatsu, S. I. (2021). Sex pheromone of the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) of a "Far East. population Okinawa Japan. *Appl. Entomology Zoology* 56, 19–25. doi: 10.1007/s13355-020-00703-9
- Wan, J., Huang, C., Li, C. Y., Zhou, H. X., Ren, Y. L., Li, Z. Y., et al. (2021). Biology, invasion and management of the agricultural invader: Fall armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *J. Integr. Agric.* 20, 646–663. doi: 10.1016/S2095-3119(20)63367-6
- Wang, W. Y., Wu, X. Q., Wen, T. Y., Feng, Y., and Zhang, Y. (2022). Terpene production varies in *Pinus thunbergii* Parl. with different levels of resistance, with potential effects on pinewood nematode behavior. *Forests* 13, 1140. doi: 10.3390/f13071140
- War, A. R., Sharma, H. C., Paulraj, M. G., War, M. Y., and Ignacimuthu, S. (2011). Herbivore induced plant volatiles. Their role in plant defense for pest management. *Plant Signaling Behav.* 6, 1973–1978. doi: 10.4161/psb.6.12.18053
- Weber, D. C. (2015). *Trissolcus japonicus* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae) emerges in North America. *J. Hymenoptera Res.* 43, 119–128. doi: 10.3897/JHR.43.4661
- Weber, D. C., Morrison, W. R., Khirman, A., Rice, K. B., Leskey, T. C., Rodriguez-Saona, C., et al. (2017). Chemical ecology of *Halyomorpha halys*: discoveries and applications. *J. Pest Sci.* 90, 989–1008. doi: 10.1007/s10340-017-0876-6
- Werre, S., Marwitz, R., Man in 't Veld, W. A., De Cock, A. W. A. M., Bonants, P. J. M., De Weerd, M., et al. (2001). *Phytophthora ramorum* sp. nov., a new pathogen on *Rhododendron* and *Viburnum*. *Mycological Res.* 105, 1155–1165. doi: 10.1016/S0953-7562(08)61986-3
- Westbrook, J., Fleischer, S., Jairam, S., Meagher, R., and Nagoshi, R. (2019). Multigenerational migration of fall armyworm, a pest insect. *Ecosphere* 10, e02919. doi: 10.1002/ecs2.v10.11
- Wu, D., Yan, Y., and Cui, J. (1997). Sex pheromone components of *Helicoverpa armigera*; chemical analysis and field tests. *Entomologia Sin.* 4, 350–356. doi: 10.1111/j.1744-7917.1997.tb00109.x
- Xu, F. (2008). "Recent advances in the integrated management of the Pine Wood Nematode in China." in *Pine wilt disease*. Eds. B. G. Zhao, K. Futai, J. R. Sutherland and Y. Takeuchi (Springer, Tokyo), 323–333.
- Xu, H., Li, G., Liu, M., and Xing, G. (2006). Oviposition deterrents in larval frass of the cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae): chemical identification and analysis by electroantennogram. *J. Insect Phys.* 52, 320–326. doi: 10.1016/j.jinsphys.2005.11.011
- Xu, Y., Tong, Z., Zhang, X., Zhang, X., Luo, Z., Shao, W., et al. (2021). Plant volatile organic compound (E)-2-hexenal facilitates *Botrytis cinerea* infection of fruits by inducing sulfate assimilation. *New Phytol.* 231, 432–446. doi: 10.1111/nph.v231.1
- Yactayo-Chang, J. P., Mendoza, J., Willms, S. D., et al. (2021). Zea mays volatiles that influence oviposition and feeding behaviors of *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *J. Chem. Ecol.* 47, 799–809. doi: 10.1007/s10886-021-01302-w
- Yan, Z. G., and Wang, C. Z. (2006). Similar attractiveness of maize volatiles induced by *Helicoverpa armigera* and *Pseudaletia separata* to the generalist parasitoid *Campoletis chloridae*. *Entomologia Experimentalis Applicata* 118, 87–96. doi: 10.1111/j.1570-7458.2006.00368.x
- Yan, Z., Yan, Y., and Wang, C. (2005). Attractiveness of tobacco volatiles induced by *Helicoverpa armigera* and *Helicoverpa assulta* to *Campoletis chloridae*. *Chin. Sci. Bull.* 50, 1334–1341. doi: 10.1360/982005-388
- Yang, X., Tyler, B. M., and Hong, C. (2017). An expanded phylogeny for the genus *Phytophthora*. *IMA Fungus* 8, 355–384. doi: 10.5598/ima fungus.2017.08.02.09
- Yang, X., Wyckhuys, K. A. G., Jia, X., Nie, F., and Wu, K. (2021). Fall armyworm invasion heightens pesticide expenditure among Chinese smallholder farmers. *J. Environ. Manage.* 282, 111949. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.111949
- Zamora, P., Rodríguez, V., Renedo, F., Sanz, A. V., Dominguez, J. C., Pérez-Escobar, G., et al. (2015). First report of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* causing pine wilt disease on *Pinus radiata* in Spain. *Plant Dis.* 99, 1449. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-03-15-0252-PDN
- Zhang, J. P., Salcedo, C., Fang, Y. L., Zhang, R. J., and Zhang, Z. N. (2012). An overlooked component: (Z)-9-tetradecenal as a sex pheromone in *Helicoverpa armigera*. *J. Insect Physiol.* 58, 1209–1216. doi: 10.1016/j.jinsphys.2012.05.018
- Zhao, L., Mota, M., Vieira, P., Butcher, R. A., and Sun, J. (2014). Interspecific communication between pinewood nematode, its insect vector, and associated microbes. *Trends Parasitol.* 30, 299–308. doi: 10.1016/j.pt.2014.04.007
- Zhong, Y. Z., Zhang, J. P., Ren, L. L., Tang, R., Zhan, H. X., Chen, G. H., et al. (2017). Behavioral responses of the egg parasitoid *Trissolcus japonicus* to volatiles from adults of its stink bug host, *Halyomorpha halys*. *J. Pest Sci.* 90, 1097–1105. doi: 10.1007/s10340-017-0884-6
- Zobel, E. S., Hooks, C. R. R., and Dively, G. P. (2016). Seasonal abundance, host suitability, and feeding injury of the brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae), in selected vegetables. *J. Economic Entomology* 109, 1289–1302. doi: 10.1093/jee/tow055